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SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING OF WATER QUALITY

FP6-034472 - WARMER D.11

by

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Introduction

“Water quality” has undoubtedly become a subject of concern for politics, environment agencies, chemical industry, planners, and to the general public as well, because of its potential impact on human health, environment and quality of life.

Operational monitoring of water quality is performed at national level in almost all industrialised countries, although most of third countries have more recently started local programs to deal with this issue. International concerted actions and agreements/treaties are in progress, especially in Europe, to harmonise the techniques and methods of sampling and measurement of a number of key-parameters of crucial importance for an efficient monitoring of water quality at regional level. The approach for this monitoring is met through combined use of both a large suite of well established and innovative *in situ* instrumentation, remote sensing monitoring from satellite and aircrafts as well as advanced numerical modelling tools including data assimilation.

During the last decades, “Earth observation industry” has exploded: an average of ten to twenty new EO sensors are yearly launched worldwide, the former research-limited user community has been joined by operational users who want to exploit this source of information to improve their services, the limited access to EO data has been turned into a market place. However, a gap still exists between operational users who required usable information, conformed to their tasks and “enablers” (value-added industry) who are in charge of receiving, processing and distributing EO data and derived information. This knowledge gap is described as: “on one side are the scientists and engineers who know how to measure variables in the Earth system from space, but have little, if any idea, of what the real information requirements of operational users with economic, social, strategic, political or environmental objectives may be, and on the other side are the operational users (information consumers), each of whom expresses their information requirements in different ways using the jargon of their particular discipline, and has little, if any, knowledge of what can be done to deliver information from spaceborne platforms, how it can benefit from them or what it is worth”, McDonald (1998).

This report intends to assessing how spaceborne observations can significantly contribute to water quality monitoring in the coastal zone, and in inland water bodies, and how EO techniques meet or could meet operational user requirements. The two Earth Observation (EO) applications considered here are, 1) monitoring of coastal waters, and 2) monitoring of inland waters (lakes and rivers). Spaceborne remote sensing is considered to have a large potential for future growth. Major progress has been achieved in this respect though the European initiative Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) under which several services integrating satellite Earth observation data are under development, assessment and implementation. Several operational GMES service lines will be in place from 2008.

The WARMER (Water Risk Management in Europe) aims at developing an integrated information system of *in situ* stations, remote sensing and information integration for risk management in aquatic environments - both coastal and in land waters. This project report (deliverable D.11 – “Satellite remote sensing of water quality”) focus on the role of use of satellite remote sensing data sources to be used in combination with the other information

sources, in particular the in situ monitoring buoy technology to be developed within the project. The report is a first iteration of the screening and selection of appropriate remote sensing information sources tailored for the WARMER project concept.

For the applications to be developed in WARMER it is required to get information available at a high spatial resolution in order to monitor water emergency situations of limited geographical extent, but with high concentrations of contaminants in the aquatic environment.

In order to meet the spatial requirement for high-resolution information this project will focus on medium to high resolution imaging sensors systems, which can be categorized in three major groups of satellite remote sensing sensors:

- Visible and Near-infrared sensors
- Thermal infrared sensors
- Active microwave radar sensors, i.e. Synthetic Aperture Radars (SAR)

Experience documents that monitoring of the aquatic environmental can be done more complete through synergistic applications of information from various satellite sensors systems, some examples of these applications are addressed in this report.

In order to meet the spatial requirement for high-resolution information also the information retrieved from airborne sensor systems will also be considered.

Visible and Near-infrared satellite remote sensing sensors

Before proceeding further in the technical aspects of the study, it seems necessary to give some background on the specificity of remote sensing of water bodies. In this section, an introduction to the physics behind EO of water bodies is given, with emphasis on optical remote sensing.

OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF THE WATER: DEFINITIONS

The report starts with some basic optical definitions from the aquatic medium to be used in the following sections.

Relation between *radiant flux* F and *radiant intensity* I : $dI = d^2F / d\omega$

Definition of *irradiance* E : $dE = d^2F / ds = dI \cos\theta / r^2$

Definition of *radiance* L : $L = d^2F / ds \cos\theta d\omega = dI / ds \cos\theta$

Other Terminology used includes;

Reflectance: the ratio of the radiant flux to the incident radiant flux:

$$\rho = F_r / F_0$$

Transmittance: the ratio of the transmitted radiant flux to the incident radiant flux

$$T = F_t / F_0$$

Absorptance: the ratio of the radiant flux lost from a beam by the means of the absorption to the incident flux

$$A = F_a / F_0$$

Scatterance: the ratio of the radiant flux scattered from a beam, to the incident flux

$$B = F_b / F_0$$

Attenuance: the ratio of the radiant flux lost from a beam of infinitesimal width by the means of the absorption and scattering to the incident flux

$$C = F_c / F_0$$

$$1 - C = (1 - A)(1 - B) = T$$

Absorption coefficient: the internal absorptance of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$a = -\Delta A / \Delta r$$

for an homogeneous medium: $a_r = -\ln(1 - A)$

Scattering coefficient: the internal scatterance of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$b = -\Delta B / \Delta r$$

for an homogeneous medium: $b_r = -\ln(1 - B)$

Attenuation coefficient: the internal attenuation of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$c = -\Delta C / \Delta r$$

$$c = a + b$$

for an homogeneous medium: $c_r = -\ln(1 - C) = -\ln(T)$

Together with the volume scattering function (i.e., the angular distribution of the light scattered by a unit volume), the absorption, scattering and attenuation coefficients are the

inherent optical properties (IOPs) of the water. These quantities are independent of the light field distribution.

Irradiance ratio or volume reflectance: the ratio of the upward to the downward irradiance at a depth in the sea.

$$R = E_u / E_d$$

(Vertical/diffuse) *Attenuation coefficient of a quantity H* (e.g. radiance, irradiance): the vertical gradient of the logarithm of the quantity

$$K = -d(\ln H) / dz = -(1 / H)(dH / dz)$$

Volume reflectance and diffuse attenuation coefficient are apparent optical properties (AOPs) of the water. These quantities are dependent of the light field distribution.

Refractive index: the phase velocity of radiant energy in free space divided by the phase velocity of the same energy in a specified medium. It is equal to the sine of the angle of incidence (in vacuo) to the sine of the angle of refraction. Symbol: *n*
Optical length: The geometrical length of a path multiplied with the total attenuation coefficient associated with the path.

$$T = cr$$

THE COLOUR OF WATER

The propagation of downwelling direct solar and diffuse radiation through natural water bodies results not only in elastic scattering and absorption by water molecules but also in a variety of photon interactions with the co-existing water constituents of different nature. The radiative transfer mechanisms governing the spectral composition of the light emerging from the water surface ultimately determine the water colour as it is perceived by a human eye. The inorganic and organic water constituents, often called *colour-producing agents* (CPAs), responsible for water colour are generally referred to as *water quality parameters*. Therefore, the water colour can be considered as a convolution of light interactions with CPAs and H₂O molecules, and as such is not infrequently exploited as a quality characterizing the current ecological/sanitary/resources status of the aquatic environment. The CPAs related to retrieval from ocean colours satellite information sources are mainly related to the abundance of chlorophyll-a, suspended sediments, dissolved organic matter and water transparency. Chemical compound and dissolved or suspended compounds in low concentrations in the water are in general not detectable from satellite remote sensing, however detection of the water circulation and waters masses of different origin can be used to characterize the environmental conditions. Synergies between information from different Earth observation data sources are also valuable to improve the understanding of the actual environmental conditions, although they may not directly provide information on the pollutants of major concern.

Utilization of water colour for assessment of water quality parameters can be achieved through the application of the accomplishments in aquatic optics attained over many decades. Indeed, an adequate knowledge of photon propagation in natural water, as a scattering and absorbing medium, can serve as a basis for development of procedures (algorithms) that would give a scientifically justifiable meaning to the optical data collected from above the water-air interface, and a means of retrieving the concentrations of CPAs.

Aquatic optics can be subdivided according to whether the natural water body is saline (oceanic), inland or fresh (limnological), or coastal (often brackish). The degree of optical complexity of a natural water body/mass, and hence the description/modeling of its interactions with the visible light, is, in general, related to its proximity to land masses.

Accordingly both the optical conditions of the actual waters pixels imaged and the distances to surrounding land pixels are of importance when remote sensing applications are implemented.

Morel and Prieur (1977) have suggested a bipartite division of the world oceans waters, according to which all natural waters are either Case I or Case II waters. In Case I waters, phytoplankton together with accompanying and co-varying products of their life cycles (debris) as well as some microscopic organisms such as flagellates, bacteria and viruses (which are also indigenous to off-shore/mid-oceanic waters) are the principal agents determining the variations in optical properties of sea water. If present, the substances other than phytoplankton are generally relatively scarce, and the optical properties of Case I waters can thus be modelled in most cases just as a function of phytoplankton concentration alone (Sathyendranath, 2000).

The optical properties of Case II waters, unlike Case I waters, are influenced not only by phytoplankton and the substances originating from the phytoplankton's life cycle evolution, but also by other substances that were generated independently of phytoplankton, notably inorganic/terrigenous particulate matter in suspension and dissolved organics. Their content in the water column is often abundant enough to compete with phytoplankton in influencing the resultant optical properties of Case II waters, thus rendering such waters optically very complex. This optical complexity of Case II waters rapidly escalates when approaching the coast. Naturally, it progressively complicates the task of interpreting water colour with the goal of inferring the composition and concentrations of CPAs.

It is further aggravated by the fact that unlike oceanographic optics, which has since long ago benefited from rapid advances in development of sophisticated submersible spectrometric instrumentation, limnological/coastal optics has not enjoyed the same quality and variety of hydro-optical devices with the appropriate spectral resolution within the appropriate spectral region, the dynamic range of sensitivity, and the required vertical resolution of measured quantities. This lack of dedicated instrumentation has hindered and still is hindering the progress in acquiring/collecting *in situ* data on the optical properties of Case II waters. The WARMER concept of integration of *in situ* and remote sensing methods will improve this situation.

Moreover, the optical complexity of Case II waters (both in terms of their composition and characteristic abundance of CPAs) implies in many cases the necessity of considering a number of mechanisms of photon interactions with molecules and particles residing in the water column and as well as with the bottom (in the case of optically shallow waters), which are less important when dealing with Case I waters. It requires along with multifaceted *in situ* hydro-optical data a development of new theoretical approaches to account for the impacts of such interactions (e.g. fluorescence) on the upwelling radiance and, hence, the water colour perceived by a (airborne or satellite) remote sensing sensor system.

This, in turn, entails the necessity of applying/developing new, much more sophisticated techniques for the retrieval of CPAs. Furthermore, when Case II waters are heavily laden with CPAs, the upwelling radiance can be very weak and account for only 1 to 2% (sometimes even less!) of the radiation captured by a satellite sensor. In Case I waters the surface signal accounts for typically 10-20% of the radiation captured by the satellite sensor. The rest of the captured signal is mostly due to the contribution of the intervening atmosphere, often called *path radiance*, and, to a lesser degree, the diffuse sky light reflected from the water surface, sun glint being automatically avoided by appropriate tilting of the sensor. It implies extremely high accuracy measurements for a proper removal of both the atmospheric path radiance and surface reflection.

Finally, typical time and space scales of features to be monitored in coastal and inland water bodies are often so specific that a simple adaptation of sensors built for Case I water environments will not meet the challenges associated with the remote sensing of Case II water resources. A successful remote-sensing mission in Case II waters necessitates the use of specialized satellite sensors designed to meet both the ground resolution and repeat cycle requirements arising from the nature of the phenomena to be studied/monitored, the spatial and temporal resolution of complementary *in situ* measurements (that remain necessary and should be carefully designed!) as well as the application of the derived information products. Even though Case II waters constitute only a small fraction (about 8%) of the total water-covered area of our planet, their economic, social and ecological significance cannot be overlooked. Sixty per cent of the human population lives in the coastal zone, defined by Pernetta and Milliman (1995) as “the region from 200 m above to 200 m below mean sea level”. Two thirds of the world’s large cities are coastal ones. Coastal waters account for 14% of global ocean primary production, 90% of world fish catch, 75-90% of global sink of suspended river load (Parslow *et al.*, 2000). Human recreational activities and tourism, important habitats, coral reefs inclusive, rapidly-growing mariculture - far from being a complete list of the significance of coastal and inland waters - warrant the efforts at national and international levels to achieve sustainable management of Case II water resources. Remote sensing can and must play an important role here in timely surveillance and diagnosis of current trends/dynamics in the ecological state of coastal and inland water bodies, like those being of concern to monitor in the WARMER project.

COLOUR PRODUCING AGENTS IN WATER

Natural waters are complex media comprising living, non-living, and once-living material that may be present in aqueous solution or suspension. Together with air bubbles and inhomogeneities resulting from small-scale circulation eddies, all these components determine the bulk optical properties of natural water bodies.

Pure water is defined as a *chemically* pure substance composed of a mixture of several water isotopes, each of different molecular mass.

The principal organisms present in water are *plankton*, a collective term encompassing all vegetable and animal organisms suspended in water (either hovering or floating), with limited ability to resist the current, and not rigidly connected to the bottom. Plankton include animal organisms (*zooplankton*), algal plant organisms (*phytoplankton*), bacteria (*bacterioplankton*), and lower plant forms such as *algal fungi*.

These organisms represent the lowest levels in the food chain relationships involving not only the plankton (and their essential nutrients), but also higher forms of aquatic life. *Phytoplankton* consume nutrients (biogenes) from their surrounding waters and in the presence of subsurface sunlight synthesize these nutrients into organic matter through the process of *primary production*. Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton. As consequences of their vital functions and their mortality, zooplankton generate *secondary* organic matter.

The number of *bacterioplankton* reaches 10^5 cells per cm^3 in oligotrophic waters, a figure that becomes considerably larger as the water becomes more rich in nutrients, reaching about 10^9 cells per cm^3 . The colourless part of bacterioplankton, of course, do not produce an impact on the aquatic colour, although they likely strongly contribute to scattering (see below). The coloured bacterioplankton, possesses pigments that are comparable to those of phytoplankton: the absorption spectra of the bacterial chlorophyll are similar to those of algal chlorophylls, except that the peaks are shifted towards longer wavelengths.

Algal fungi, along with bacterioplankton, are the sole transformers of organic matter in natural waters into compounds digestible by most aquatic microorganisms. It should be underscored that the complete lack of fungal coloration, coupled with their low concentrations, results in algal fungi producing no optical impact on natural waters at scales relevant to remote sensing.

The concerted action of algal fungi and bacterioplankton in the decomposition of the available aquatic organic matter in suspension determines the dynamics of the food chain at the lowest trophic level. Due to this low level food chain dynamics, dissolved organic matter (*dom*) (termed the *autochthonous dom* component) is indigenous to natural waters. Lakes and marine/oceanic *coastal* waters are also recipients of *dom* inputs from terrestrial run-off and river discharges which contribute an *allochthonic dom* component. These run-off and river discharge inputs also introduce a suspended inorganic matter (*sim*) component to non-Case I waters.

Phytoplankton cells and colonies exist in a variety of shapes (filaments, ribbons, stars, etc.) and sizes. Reynolds (1984) present statistical data on the phytoplankton sizes, which show that unicellular algae possess nominal mean maximum dimensions in the range 5 to 40 μm . The corresponding range for filaments would be 80 to 150 μm , for ribbon colonies 60 to several hundred μm , and for mucilaginous colonies 50 to 200 μm .

The coloration of phytoplankton cells is dependent on their pigment content and composition. Phytoplankton pigments serve as the collectors and suppliers of energy for the photosynthesis, the basic mechanism in plant growth. There are three basic types of photosynthesising pigments: *chlorophylls*, *carotenoids*, and *phycobilins*. Chlorophylls and carotenoids are present in all algal species. Phycobilins are additionally present in blue-green algae and dinoflagellates. The principal chlorophyll absorption occurs in the short wavelength (blue) and, generally to a lesser degree, the long wavelength (red) regions in the visible spectrum. Carotenoid absorption peaks in the blue spectral region. Phycobilin absorption strongly depends upon species with peaks at green, yellow, or short red wavelengths.

Zooplankton, are in dynamic equilibrium with the other components of the aquatic food chain. Depending upon the trophic status of non-Case I waters, the concentrations of zooplankton can easily exceed several hundreds of thousands of plankters per m^3 , varying in size from 30 μm to $> 2 \text{ mm}$. Since zooplankton is grazers of phytoplankton and phytoplankton are chlorophyll-bearing biota, chlorophyll is invariably present within the digestive tracts of zooplankters. Thus this presence of chlorophyll and its derivatives would suggest that absorption and scattering of zooplankton might display features comparable to the counter-characteristics of phytoplankton. However, we are not aware of data that would support or refute this hypothesis. Besides, the zooplankter concentration is generally low (compared to bacterioplankton and phytoplankton, see below), and on this basis, zooplankton is tentatively considered to be ineffective for light transfer through the water body.

Inorganic salts dissolved in natural waters affect absorption and scattering within the water column. However, their most significant absorption lies at the ultraviolet, rather than visible, wavelengths since the electron transition bands of dissolved inorganic salts exist at $\lambda < 300 \text{ nm}$ (Shifrin, 1983). The contribution of scattering by dissolved inorganic salts accounts for about 20 to 30% of total scattering in offshore/pelagic oceanic waters of average salinity of 35 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. In inland fresh water bodies, as well as brackish coastal waters (diluted with fresh water arriving as river runoff as well as with flows of rain and snowmelt accumulations from the catchment), the contribution to scattering by dissolved inorganic salts in non-Case I water is strongly reduced.

Dissolved organic matter (dom) concentrations are the consequence of either photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton (autochthonic) or direct inputs of terrestrial matter (allochthonic). Of the total organic matter resulting from phytoplankton photosynthesis, up to 20% can be released to the ambient aquatic environment through *metabolic egestion* (Gorlenko *et al.*, 1974). These egesta are, in general, assimilated by bacterioplankton, however, in nutrient-limited waters, the phytoplankton themselves may compete with bacterioplankton for such egesta assimilation.

In fresh and brackish waters *dom* is not conservative, but rather undergoes various biological and *photochemical* transformations (Bertilsson and Travník, 2000) before the residual of *dom* is eventually discharged into the oceans. Solar radiation, particularly in the ultraviolet, has the potential (especially in oligotrophic rather than eutrophic non-Case I waters) to alter the spectral and molecular properties of *dom* (mostly allochthonous *dom*), and to promote its degradation, either directly through *photooxidation* or indirectly by increased *bioavailability*. Yellowness/brownishness is a characteristic hue of waters containing *dom* in large amounts, which is due to yellow and brown melanoids. These melanoids, however, comprise only a fraction ranging between 10 and 40% of the aquatic *dom*.

Since allochthonic *dom* is absent from mid-oceanic (Case I) waters, and the autochthonic *dom* should be low due to generally low nutrient levels in Case I waters, the aquatic humus in Case I waters co-varies with phytoplankton (or its proxy, chlorophyll), keeping in mind that the mid oceanic waters are also nearly devoid of suspended minerals. As it will be discussed in further chapters, this facilitates algorithm-development for remote sensing of Case I waters that is not available for remote sensing of inland and coastal waters.

Aquatic humus, *dom*, concentrations in oceanic waters are generally very low in the range 0.001-0.005 g Carbon per m³. However, it should be pointed out that there are observations (Church *et al.*, 2002) indicating that a small fraction of the annually produced organic matter in some locations of the world oceans can escape biological utilization on time scales of months to years. A conjecture has been put forward that it might be a result of reorganization of dynamics of plankton community, which brings about significant alterations to cycling of organic matter in the ecosystem. It is believed that can be driven by basin-scale climate variability.

The concentration or density of *dom* is usually given in the unit grams of *carbon* per unit volume since carbon constitutes approximately *half* the *dom* by weight. Because of this *dom* will here and henceforth be named *doc* (where *c* stands for carbon). The concentration of *doc* in oceanic waters is about four orders of magnitude below the concentrations of dissolved salts. However, the optical impact of *doc* is stronger than that of dissolved salts. Although *doc* does not significantly impact scattering within the water column, it considerably increases absorption. In inland and coastal waters, however, *doc* concentrations are often considerably higher: *doc* ranges from a 1 to 2 g C per m³ in oligo/mesotrophic waters to 20-25 g C per m³ in hyper-eutrophic waters (Romankevich, 1977).

The absorption by *doc* decreases exponentially from short to long wavelengths in the visible spectrum. The observed *doc* absorption in the visible spectrum is a “tail” of electron transition absorption bands located in the ultraviolet (UV) part of the spectrum. The spectral dependence of the absorption coefficient $a_{ys}(\lambda)$ for the coloured fraction of *doc* (so called *yellow substance*), can be approximated well by a simple exponential function (Zepp and Schlotzhauer, 1981):

$$a_{ys}(\lambda) = a_{ys}(\lambda_0) \exp[-s(\lambda - \lambda_0)], \quad (2.1)$$

where s is a slope parameter that is assumed to be independent of wavelength λ . Thus the constancy of the shape of the $a_{ys}(\lambda)$ versus λ curve in eq. (2.1) enables the selection of a reference wavelength, λ_0 , upon which to compare the yellow substance concentrations of different waters. The selection of $\lambda_0 = 400$ nm is certainly appropriate since it represents the maximum a_{ys} in the visible spectrum. However, $\lambda_0 = 440$ nm is also frequently encountered in the published literature.

To date, little attention has been directed towards the possible effects of *doc* on the scattering properties of natural waters (convenient to set $b_{doc}(\lambda)$ to zero). Although such neglect of the scattering from organic matter that resides in the water column is justified for true molecular solutions, there is sometimes a very substantial fraction of “dissolved” organic matter that is not in true molecular solution, but exists in colloidal form, which can impact the bulk scattering coefficient characterizing the optical properties of the water column. More importantly, a certain, presumably small fraction of *doc* can fluoresce with the emission maximum (a) located in a wide spectral region extending from about 310 to 520 nm depending on the nature of *doc* and the excitation wavelength (Coble, 1994).

Suspended matter. All natural water bodies contain suspended matter consisting of organic and inorganic matter under the collective term *seston*. Seston is extremely diverse in origin and in composition, and includes mineral terrigenous particles, plankton (see above), detritus (largely residual products of the decomposition of phytoplankton and zooplankton cells as well as macrophytic plants), volcanic ash particles, particulates resulting from *in situ* chemical reactions, and particles of anthropogenic origin.

Suspended inorganic (mineral) matter (sm). The presence of terrigenous suspended particles is a consequence of river discharge, coastal erosion, catchment run-off, long and short range transport of atmospheric particulates followed by dry and wet deposition.

The main constituents found in *sm* derived from surface soils are quartz, feldspars, calcite, dolomite, gypsum, mica, kaolinite, illite, montmorillonite, palygorskite, chlorite (for ref. see Sokolik and Toon, 1999). The real and imaginary parts of the complex refractive index for the atmospherically-transported *sm* vary at $\lambda = 500$ nm between 1.4 and about 2.8 (and even 3.4 for hematite), and < 0.00005 to typically 0.001 (for hematite up to 0.1), respectively. The *single scattering albedo*, $\omega = b/c$, at $\lambda = 500$ nm is between 0.95 and 1.0 (it decreases down to 0.8 at $\lambda \leq 300$ nm, but it is about 0.6 over large parts of the visible spectrum for hematite). The *asymmetry parameter* (b_f/b) is generally found between 0.68 and 0.89 (Sokolik and Toon, 1999). According to Kondratyev *et al.*, (1999), fine clay particulates rarely exceed 3 to 4 μm in diameter, silt particles are in the range 5 to 40 μm , very fine grain sands fall in the range 40 to 130 μm , and coarse grain sands are in the range 130 to 250 μm . In Lake Ladoga, seston concentrations range from 0.1 to 12.0 g per m^3 , with suspended minerals accounting for about 50 to 97% (Multi-author, 1987). Suspended mineral concentrations in Lake Ontario have been reported in the range 0.2 to 8.9 g per m^3 (Bukata *et al.*, 1995).

Along with the plankton, inorganic suspended particulates dictate the manner in which the subsurface light field is distributed in the natural water body and, therefore, have to be considered both in terms of their absorption and scattering properties. About 90% of the coarse fraction of the terrigenous matter is found within the near shore zone.

Suspended organic matter. Suspended organics in natural water bodies contain planktonic organisms and detritus particles. As pointed out earlier, the plankton consist of algal fungi, bacteria (bacterioplankton), micro algae (phytoplankton) and micro animal organisms

(zooplankton). With the only exception for algal fungi (which are transparent and colourless and thus have a refraction index practically indistinguishable from that of water), all planktonic species are optically active in the visible spectrum as a result of

- 1) light absorption, mostly, stemming from pigments either indigenous to the aquatic cells (bacterioplankton and phytoplankton) or otherwise acquired through trophic chain interactions (zooplankton) (Karnaukhov, 1988);
- 2) light scattering by cells/bodies, which are generally of complex and very irregular geometry and inner structure. It is due to their small size that the viruses and bacteria have the highest backscattering ratio (defined as the ratio of backscattering to the total scattering) among autotrophic and heterotrophic plankton (van de Hulst, 1957).

When deciding on the eligibility of water co-existing constituents for the status of principal CPAs that dictate the bulk water optical/colour properties, their absolute and relative concentrations become the criterion. The Lake Ladoga water can be considered as a good example. In spring, the bacterioplankton number concentration (C_{bp}) in the coastal zone may attain 1.5-2.0 million cells cm^{-3} , whereas within the pelagic region, C_{bp} does not generally exceed 0.1 to 1.0 million cells cm^{-3} .

In summer, C_{bp} decreases in coastal waters to about 0.5 to 0.65 million cells cm^{-3} but increases up to 10 to 20 million cm^{-3} in the central part of the lake. In autumn, C_{bp} is about 0.6 to 0.7 million/ cm^{-3} and is nearly uniformly distributed throughout the lake (Viljanen *et al.*, 1996).

The phytoplankton concentration (C_{php}) within the top (0-10 m) layer varies significantly depending on the vegetation period. The average C_{php} value might reach the level of several hundred thousand cells/l in the pelagic part of the lake and several million cells per liter in the littoral zone (Viljanen *et al.*, 1996). The typical concentrations of zooplankton (C_{zp}) in the surface waters (0-20 m) of the littoral zone are several hundreds of plankters per cubic meter. Generally, C_{zp} is, however, somewhat lower in the pelagic zone (Viljanen *et al.*, 1996).

Consequently, taking the above numbers, the concentration ratios of bacterioplankton / phytoplankton / zooplankton for maximal and minimal values of are as follows: $10^{12}/10^6/10^2$ and $10^{11}/10^5/10^1$. Although, in some vegetation periods (of rather short duration), the concentration of phytoplankton and zooplankton could be of the same order of magnitude in inland water bodies (Viljanen *et al.*, 1996) it can, nevertheless, be assumed that zooplankton, are hardly be generally considered as a major colour producing agent (CPA).

Detritus. Detritus, as defined above, consists of suspended organic and partly mineralized particulates, which are fragments of dead plankton and fecal pellets of zooplankton. The detritus content in water can vary substantially depending on vegetation period and trophic level. The detritus concentration is closely related to the phytoplankton content, and it reaches 10 to 30% of C_{php} . Although, these concentration ratios are typical of Lake Ladoga, however, they are also valid for other temperate inland fresh water bodies (Petrova, 1990).

Air bubbles. In the upper layers of natural waters trapped air bubbles are mainly generated by injection of air by breaking waves. The refractive index of air bubbles *per se* is 0.75. The majority of the air bubbles injected into the surface layers of natural waters are unstable. However, for oceanic air bubbles with long residence times, a bubble concentration of about 10^5 to 10^6 m^{-3} and even as large as 2.13×10^7 was observed (for ref. see Yan *et al.*, 2002). The

sizes (radius, r) of air bubbles vary from about 0.01 to about 350 μm , following on average the bubble size distribution $n(r) \sim r^{-4}$ (Stramski, 1994). The bubbles are distributed within the top layer of the ocean, and observations indicate that the thickness of this layer can vary over a large range from 0.25 to 36 m. There is evidence (for ref. see Yan *et al.*, 2002) that some bubble clouds could reach mean depths of about $4 H_s$, where H_s is the significant wave height. But some bubble clouds can extend down to approximately $6 H_s$: they are frequently observed at depths of 6 to 11 m and even down to 36 m (Wu, 1988). Given the bubble number density that has typically been reported from measurements in the sea (i.e. ranging, as we saw above, from about 10^5 to 10^7 cm^{-3}), the bubble population will significantly influence the scattering processes in the ocean, especially in oligotrophic waters.

Often water bubbles are covered with organic films mainly composed mainly of proteins or lipids. The thickness of such coatings of bubbles in seawater has been estimated to range from 0.01 μm for lipids to 1 μm for proteins. The mean relative refractive indices of the coating substances ($n \approx 1.20$ for proteins and $n \approx 1.10$ for lipids) are quite different from those of clean water bubbles (see above). As shown by Zhang *et al.* (1998), this implies that the coated bubbles scatter stronger than clean bubbles. Any way, these air-bubbles-related scattering centres should also result in attenuation of downwelling radiation because of absorption, as the imaginary part of the refractive index of coated bubbles lies between 0.001 and 0.006, which is similar to the mean imaginary index of refraction of phytoplankton cells. The latter value is probably close to the maximum value for chlorophyll in the red absorption band (Morel, 1990). But also backscattered upwelling radiation is increased. Both effects change volume reflectance, which then may be erroneously attributed to the presence of suspended organic or inorganic particulates.

According to Zhang *et al.* (1998), the mean scattering efficiency factor of bubbles is comparable to those of nanoplankton (2–20) μm and microplankton (20–200) μm . However, for the *backscattering* ratio/efficiency, ranging from 0.02 for clean/uncoated bubbles to as high as 0.08 for bubbles with a 0.1- μm thick protein cover, bubbles are at least one order of magnitude more efficient in backscattering than planktonic organisms. In general, the role of clean/coated bubbles in increasing/modifying the resultant volume reflectance will decrease as the concentration of phytoplankton and suspended minerals increases. However, this decreasing contribution will shrink with increasing λ . This is due to b_b being spectrally flat for both clean and coated bubbles (Zhang *et al.*, 1998), whereas it decreases with λ for seston.

Therefore, the air bubbles can generally be a reason of a non-zero upwelling radiance in the red and near infrared part of the spectrum in phytoplankton-free deep oceans, thus invalidating the assumption of black water that lies at the basis of most atmospheric correction procedures for ocean colour remote sensing data.

The extreme diversity of the organic and inorganic components of inland and marine/oceanic waters, coupled with the temporal and spatial variability of the composition of these waters, presents a severe obstacle to define the major players in water optics. Thus, a manageable number of these components (or surrogates/proxies to these components) has to be selected for an adequate physical model that adequately describes the optical properties of a natural water body.

At the same time, based on some *a priori* knowledge from molecular spectroscopy, some natural water constituents can be confidently ruled out from the list of those substances, which we qualified as the main CPAs. For instance, *dissolved atmospheric gases* with the sole exception of oxygen do not absorb appreciably in the visible spectrum. At their small concentrations they neither can contribute considerably to molecular cumulative scattering.

Algal fungi and zooplankton are also likely to be excluded from the list of CPAs. Summarizing the above data, we suggest that the group of major CPAs for non- Case I waters should be composed of water *per se*, phytoplankton, bacterioplankton, *doc*, *sm*, detritus (in some cases), and probably air bubbles (in *oligotrophic* waters). However, literature search (Kondratyev *et al.*, 1999) indicates that, unfortunately, the data on microphysical characteristics and optical properties of bacterioplankton, detritus, and air bubbles are still scarce and do not yet allow any generalization. On the other hand, we feel that the exclusion of zooplankton, detritus, bacterioplankton, and air bubbles will not significantly detract from the discussion of the four component model: water *per se*, phytoplankton, suspended minerals (*sm*) and dissolved organics (*doc*) in Case II waters. Accordingly, the primary water quality parameters for monitoring using satellite Earth observation data includes phytoplankton, suspended minerals and dissolved organics. In the following an operational production line for delivery of such information will be outlined.

Thermal Infrared Sensors

Since the water emissivity is close to the unity in the thermal infrared domain, the water leaving radiance in the 3 μm –12 μm band can be expressed through the blackbody theory. Due to the dielectric properties of water, electromagnetic radiation do not penetrate into water depths greater than typically 1 μm in this band. The mean temperature of the water interface corresponding to this depth is generally named Sea Surface Temperature (SST). Due to the fact that this layer is also the place where other energetic processes of exchanges with the atmosphere do occur, its thermal equilibrium is subject to many artefacts (wind, vertical mixing, or stratification...). So, this method for the measurement of the water surface temperature may lead to strong discrepancies with the results offered by other ways (e.g. bucket temperature).

Starting with the Planck's law which relates the blackbody radiance L to the absolute temperature SST at a given wavelength λ :

$$L = \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k SST}} - 1}$$

The exponential dependency of the blackbody radiance from the temperature may be simplified for the needs of thermography algorithms. This may be achieved by two ways. In the microwave domain, where the water thermal emissivity is still significant, the Rayleigh-Jeans approximation permits to use a simplified relationship, which leads to a linear dependency between radiance and temperature. Expressed in this way, the radiance is also named brightness temperature. In the thermal infrared domain, the Rayleigh-Jeans is no longer valid but it is still possible to develop the Planck law in a Taylor series, and to only keep the linear term. This method may be used when the temperature variation is of the order of magnitude of 10 K, which is generally the case in satellite thermography of water surfaces on Earth. In that case, the previous equation leads to:

$$L = G \cdot SST + B$$

where G is the gain of the imaging system, and B is a bias. One may notice that in this case, L is sometimes improperly named as the brightness temperature.

Since 1978 the NOAA meteorological satellites have carried sensors in the thermal infrared spectral range. These sensors allow retrieval of the sea surface temperature (SST) at both medium spectral (typically < 1km) and absolute accuracy (< 0.1 °C). Routine observations are available in both near real-time and as archived data and can accordingly be used for monitoring purposes to e.g. to discriminate water masses of different origin.

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)

Radar sensors provide data independent of daylight and cloud conditions, making them suitable for monitoring of large ocean areas, which is difficult to monitor by other means. The SAR sensor emits a radar pulse and measures how much is scattered back from the surface (i.e. the ocean or the ground). The backscatter depends, among other things, on the surface roughness. The C-band radar backscatter (as in Radarsat and Envisat SARs) is caused by Bragg scattering by interaction of the incident radar waves with short gravity waves with wave lengths in the range of 5-7 cm. The capillary waves and short gravity waves are generated by winds blowing over the ocean surface. Under low wind conditions, the energy content in this part of the wave spectrum is low or almost zero, resulting in low radar backscatter and in dark patches in the SAR imagery. Surface film of high-viscosity material such as oil present on the sea surface will damp the Bragg waves, and give rise to dark signatures. Modulation of the Bragg waves by ocean current features and gravity waves can also lead to dampening giving rise to dark features. Therefore methods for both detection and discrimination of slicks are required in an operational oil spill monitoring service. The first set of methods is needed to identify potential contaminated areas, and the second to determine whether a suspicious slick is likely to contain oil or if it is more likely a result of some natural phenomena.

From the general point of view, the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery is defined by the ability of surface targets to reflect the radar signal toward the sensor, which may occur through two processes: the specular reflection, which covers mainly the domain of incidence angles between 0° to 20° , and the backscattering processes, which covers the incidence range between 10° to 70° . At sea surface, both phenomenon may occur, but in any case, the image intensity may be related to the reflecting ability of sea surface, through the backscattering coefficient σ :

$$\frac{P_s}{P_e} = \frac{G \cos \theta}{4\pi r^2} X_a X_r \sigma \frac{A}{4\pi r^2}$$

where:

P_s and P_e are respectively the received and the transmitted power

X_a and X_r the slant and the radial spatial resolution of the SAR system

G is the antenna gain and

θ is the incidence angle r is the range.

For SAR imaging the water surface over a range of incidence angles from about 20° to 70° , the radar backscatter is principally caused by a resonant mechanism, called Bragg scattering, where the radar energy is scattered by surface waves of approximately the same wavelength. The short surface waves are modulated by long waves and currents, causing sufficient variability that can be seen on radar imagery. For SAR imaging surface waves, the modulation is caused by three principal processes, each of which varies in strength depending on the surface wave propagation direction with respect to the radar velocity vector. For range-travelling waves, image variability is mainly produced by surface tilt, which is the change in local incidence angle of the short waves present along the long wave and by hydrodynamic interactions (also called straining), where the long waves alters the amplitude of the surface waves by convergence and divergence and airflow variations (Figure 3). For azimuth travelling waves, the principal cause of image variability results from velocity bunching where the orbital motion of the long waves themselves produces an azimuthal displacement of

the Bragg waves in the image plane (Figure 1). For ocean waves having a high-azimuth directional component, this mechanism also causes image smearing at higher azimuth wave numbers. Velocity bunching is linear for low-azimuth wave numbers (*i.e.* long and low swells), and when the altitude of the SAR platform is less than about 300 km.

Figure 1: SAR water imaging mechanisms (NASA, 1990).

Synergistic applications of Satellite EO Information Products

With increasing number of satellite Earth observations sensors available, sensitive in different spectral regions and providing complementary geo-bio-chemical environmental information, synergistic applications of multiple sensors information are developing. The potential of such synergies are described through some practical examples, given below.

EXAMPLE 1- *CHATTONELLA* BLOOM WEST JUTLAND - MAY 1998

At the beginning of May 1998, a large harmful algae bloom dominated by the flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*, probably in combination with a small amount of *Heterosigma akashiwo*, caused mass mortality of fish in farms in the Farsund and Flekkefjord area. Around 350 tonnes of salmon died, mainly mature fish. This was the first time *Chattonella* was registered in Europe, and also the first time it had appeared in such high concentrations, which resulted in the massive death of aquacultured fish. The algae specie was later observed at the western coast of Sweden, and affected the whole area of Skagerrak by the beginning of May (see Figure 2). Later high concentrations were reported along the west and northern coast of Jutland, resulting in the death of garfish, herring and sand eel. The high concentrations of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak and along the western coast of Jutland were found in water, which contained unusually high concentrations of nutrients during this time of the year. Large amounts of anthropogenic nitrate from the southern part of the North Sea probably stimulated the extreme growth of the algae bloom together with favourable sun conditions. The bloom had its maximum extension during mid-May and culminated towards the last week of the month. Through this period several high quality SeaWiFS ocean colour EO images have been available and analysed (Figure 2) together with ERS SAR and AVHRR SST (Figure 4).

During this HAB event additional ERS and Radarsat SAR data were available and has been used in the synergy analysis together with meteorological boundary layer information from ECMWF (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

The AVHRR SST image of May 15th in the western Skagerrak is partly contaminated by clouds and aircraft curtails, which are interfering and masking some of the surface gradients in the SST (Figure 3). The exact interpretation on the image is accordingly difficult, however examination of the same data source obtained on the 17th support the following interpretation. The Norwegian coastal water is colder than the offshore Skagerrak water in the area south of Kristiansand. A tongue of warm waters is breaking out through the central part of Skagerrak and extending up along the west coast of Jæren. The temperature of these water masses is at a similar level to the surface water in the central Skagerrak gyre. In the SeaWiFS ocean colour data an offshore decreasing gradient (off-shore values are 20-50% of the coastal concentrations) in the chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentrations are observed. In the central Skagerrak the inflow of colder and significantly less chlorophyll-rich (purple colour in Chl-a pigment concentration with typical values of 2-5% of the coastal water concentrations) water of Atlantic origin occurs. This inflow of waters of Atlantic origin through the North Sea is to a very large extent steered by the topography of the Norwegian Trench. This interpretation reveals that SST and Chl-a satellite based data provide similar and complementary information on water masses and their biological and geophysical conditions as well as the ocean circulation pattern. However, the expressions of this ocean circulation pattern are resolved by different strength (contrasts) in the biological Chl-a concentration and in the SST expression of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC).

Figure 2. Chlorophyll pigment concentration product from SeaWiFS over the North Sea and the Skagerrak, on (a) May 13, (b) May 15, (c) May 17, 1998. The sea surface temperature (SST) for the same dates are shown in (d)-(e). The SST data for the 13th are lacking. The time series shows the increases and decay of a *Chattonella* spp. bloom, along the west coast of Jutland, Denmark. Blue/purple indicates low pigment; red indicates high pigment. © Orbital Imaging Corps / NASA SeaWiFS project. Courtesy: Steven Groom, RSDAS/PML.

On the 15th May the air temperature from the ECMWF reanalysis data is about 11°C in this area and the SST data from AVHRR are about 1°C warmer (see Figure 2 and Figure 6). The wind speed and atmospheric boundary layer stability i.e. the temperature difference between the water surface and the air temperature, should therefore cause a higher normalised radar cross section (NRCS) along the coast of Norway than for the colder water mass further off-shore due to turbulence created by more unstable near-surface conditions (Figure 4) which is what is observed in the ERS SAR image of the 15th. The current system in the area off Lista as mapped in the SST data from the 17th is well confirmed with the model simulations for both the 15th and 17th using Nansen Center HYCOM (Figure 3), with a even more pronounced signature in the SST on the 17th.

Figure 3: HYCOM model simulations of the ocean currents and SST on respectively the 15th and 17th May, 1998.

Figure 4:
AVHRR
SAR
and
Chl-a

The
SST, ERS
image
SeaWiFS

distribution for the area in western Skagerrak and Jutland current on May 15th.
The SAR coverage area is superimposed.

Figure 5: To the upper right is shown the SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a pigment data from the 13th, 14th and 15th during the Chattonella bloom west of Jutland. ECMWF surface wind speed and direction are plotted for the 15th at noon (center upper panel). The three plots of temperature, wind speed and wind direction are obtained at the locations 1-3 indicated in the contour plot of the wind field. The wind speed in this figure ranges from 0-7m/s. Due to higher wind on the 13th (at Radersat passage) than on the 15th at ERS-2 passage, more ocean features are observed in the ERS-2 images.

Figure 6: ECMWF reanalysis of wind speed for the mornings of May 13th (06 UTC – close to Radarsat passage), 14th (12 UTC) and 15th (12 UTC – close to ERS SAR passage).

The series of data during 13-15th May 1998 illustrates the importance of the wind speed being in the right range when studying ocean features in SAR images (Figure 5). The wind during this period was easterly, turning northward in Skagerrak. The wind speeds in Skagerrak northwest of Jutland were 7 m/s on the morning of the 13th (RADARSAT), decreasing to 4,5 m/s on the 14th and further decreasing to 2 m/s on the 15th at noon (ERS) (see Figure 5). Accordingly the Radarsat image obtained on the 13th shows the clear signatures of wind streaks indicating easterly wind in agreement with the ECMWF data (Figure 5). Cloud rows aligned with the wind direction offshore from Jutland are furthermore observed in the SeaWiFS image from the 14th. The northernmost ERS-2 SAR scene from the 15th on the other hand are in the region of 2m/s wind speed and show

very clear signatures of ocean fronts, eddies and surface slicks, except for the near shore area, which has been discussed above.

Several eddies and surface slick signatures observed in the SAR image are co-located with eddies/fronts in the SeaWiFS images and the regions of high pigment concentrations as well as in the gradient areas in the SST. In particular west of Jutland the *Chattonella* bloom reached extremely high concentrations with a profound surface accumulation of the algae cells. This indicates that the bloom became so dense at the surface that it caused enough surfactants to damp out the capillary waves and being visible in the SAR image under moderate to low wind speeds, such as observed on the 15th. However, the low backscatter SAR signatures (ERS data collected two hours prior to the SeaWiFS and AVHRR passes) seems to go across fronts in the Chl-a distribution, and being more limited by gradients in the SST data. Additionally, it is interesting to notice how the western extension of high pigment concentration to the Northwest of Jutland is increasing during the days 13th to 15th as a result of the strong south easterly winds as well as the bloom being in its growth phase.

EXAMPLE 2 – A CHATTONELLA ALGAE BLOOM IN APRIL-MAY 2000

On April 18th 2000 a significant increase in the level of chlorophyll pigment concentration in the SeaWiFS data was reported by the Nansen Center to occur along the south west coast of Jutland (Pettersson et al, 2000). This high concentration of algae was confirmed in the same region two days later by a regular research cruise by Institute of Marine Research with the research vessel G.M. Dannevig. Most of the algae biomass in the region was due to phytoplankton of the class Raphidophyceae. In this class of algae, several harmful species are known, e.g. *Chattonella*, *Fibrocapsa* and *Heterosigma*. Very high concentrations of the algae *Chattonella aff. Verruculosa* was reported in the waters west from Esbjerg on April 20. The further development and subsequent decay of the bloom were efficiently monitored using EO and *in situ* data in combination. Due to the extent and rapid development of the algae bloom, the monitoring operations also went into an alert mode. During this period also satellite data were used to initiate and update (using a simple scheme of data assimilation) the model predictions of bloom development, using the IMR research forecasting algae model (NORWECOM). Clear benefits of using EO data were identified with respect to the planning of the monitoring operations, as well as in the model predictions of the development of the algae bloom. Similar algae blooms of *Chattonella* spp. and *Heterosigma* also occurred mainly in the Jutland current in 1998, but these species were in 1998 also observed blooming in Norwegian coastal waters. During these events the algae bloom caused the death of a lot of farmed as well as wild fishes.

During the days prior to May 5 a narrow tongue of water with higher pigment concentrations was observed to “break out” from the Jutland current into the central and northern parts of Skagerrak (Figure 7). These waters most likely included the *Chattonella* species and could possibly cause advection of the blooms into the coastal Norwegian waters. Dedicated field investigations were initiated in order to evaluate this observation. Analysis of the field data confirmed the observations in the satellite image, however these water masses did not reach the Norwegian coastal waters to become a treat for the aquaculture industry. The Nansen Center, Plymouth Marine Laboratory, the Institute of Marine Research and the Directorate of Fisheries were able to monitor the development and decay of this and other algae blooms using daily updated satellite images, regular, sporadic and dedicated *in situ* measurements and predictive numerical ecosystem model.

On May 4th the three EO data sources are acquired throughout the day – from a morning SST mapping at 05:54 UTC (as well as the following morning at 04:42), a noon SeaWiFS chlorophyll mapping at 12:19 UTC and an evening ERS SAR pass at 21:30 UTC (Figure 8). This implies that

the observations are not synoptic and that the environmental conditions have changed during the time evolution between the different satellites pass. However, similarities in the mapping of the ocean surface are observed in the different EO data sources. The SST data from May 5th at 04:42 UTC (not shown) have been used to supplement the interpretations of the ocean surface signatures. The regionally good weather conditions for visible and IR mapping and the low wind conditions make it possible to observe some interesting common features in the radar and optical images - starting from south going northward:

In the German Bight and off-shore of southern Jutland, very high pigment concentrations are observed in the SeaWiFS image as well as being conformed by *in situ* observations. In some areas the chlorophyll retrieval algorithm for the SeaWiFS data saturates, supporting the fact that the pigment concentrations are in fact very high (Figure 7 and Figure 9). In some of these areas (but not all) one observes a low radar backscatter signal in the ERS SAR image. Most likely this is due to the very high surface concentrations of algae biomass which is damping the surface capillary waves and causing the reduced radar return signal (see Figure 9 areas C and D). The wind pattern (Figure 10) in this region has changed significantly during the day, when wind speed earlier was up to 8 m/s. In the evening during the ERS SAR pass the wind in the entire swath of images was quite homogeneous and low (2-3 m/s). Hence the impact of the algae biomass on the damping of the surface waves might not be the only reason for the damping the radar backscatter areas observed along west Jutland. During this day there is significant reduction in the wind speed along the coast of west Denmark. At the time of the SeaWiFS passage (at 12.19 UTC) the wind speed was 4-6 m/s in the southern parts of the image. During the SAR mapping about nine hours (21:30 UTC) later the wind had decayed to about 2-3 m/s (Figure 10). In conclusion these wind conditions might have been sufficient to cause the damping of the surface capillary waves as observed in the SAR image (Figure 8 d).

In the central part of the SAR images (around 56°30'N in Figure 8) the radar backscatter signal is more homogeneous and seems to be dominated by wind blowing from Skagerrak (northeast). The wind signature in the SAR image in this region indicates somewhat higher winds than what is reported in the ECMWF data. Unfortunately only LRI data are available from this day and no absolute retrieval of the wind speed is therefore possible from the SAR data.

In the northern part of the SAR image swath (58-57°N), closer to the Norwegian coast (Figure 8) the extension and meandering of the front of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) around Lista is identified in the NOAA AVHRR sea surface temperature (SST) images, the Chlorophyll pigment concentration (slightly less contrasts, but still gradients observed), as well as in the ERS SAR backscatter resolved as current shear features. The temporal differences in the time of the EO data acquisition resolves also the advection of the fronts with time, however the shapes and extent of current features remains comparable between the different data sets.

Further offshore beyond the location of the NCC front, as well as in a larger region across the SAR image in the central Skagerrak between Denmark and Norway ($\approx 57^{\circ}15'N$), there are two regions of lower backscatter. These regions of low backscatter /surface slicks are not collocated exactly at the areas of highest Chlorophyll concentrations, which is at the tongue of higher pigment concentrations and warmer water of origin from southern Skagerrak north of Hirtshals. This feature is following the 200-meter depth contour superimposed on the SeaWiFS image (Figure 8). This high algae concentration feature was confirmed by dedicated observations performed by the Directorate of Fisheries, based on the satellite observations. South of this feature is another low-backscatter signature in the SAR image which is collocated with the frontal boundary between the water of Skagerrak and Atlantic (North Sea) origin. The system is characterized by (1) the inflow

of colder and less chlorophyll rich water as well as (2) the outflow from Skagerrak of warmer and more chlorophyll rich water. A current shear causing convergence is expected in the area, which may cause the SAR signature.

According to the Radarsat image of May 12th at 06 UTC, the wind speed in the region is higher in the near shore and particular the northern parts of the image (Figure 11). This is not exactly consistent with the ECMWF weather map of the wind distribution, however the area of the lowest wind speeds are partly consistent with the lowest backscatter values in the Radarsat image. The areas of damped radar backscatter seems to be confined close to the western boundary of the high biomass extension west of Jutland, again co-located with the boundary between the warmer coastal and the colder off-shore water masses. Assuming a homogeneous air temperature in the region the air masses over the off-shore waters is expected to be more stable than the area closer to land. No particular indications are found that the areas of high damping of the radar backscatter area co-located with particular high biomass. Accordingly it is plausible to conclude that the synergies in the image signatures is found in the region of low wind speed and that the triggering factor is the sea surface temperature and its impact on the stability of the boundary layer. Clear conclusions will require field observations during such events.

Figure 7: AVHRR SST ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 05:54 UTC, ERS-2 SAR backscatter at 21:30 UTC and SeaWiFS Chlorophyll concentration (mg/m^3) at 12:19 UTC on May 4th 2000.

SST 4th May at 05:54 UTC

SST 5th May at 04:42 UTC

SeaWiFS 4th May at 12:19 UTC (different LUT than in Figure 7 enhancing the northern part)

ERS SAR 4th May at 21:30 (super imposed SST from 5th)

Figure 8: Area enhanced selection of the data shown in Figure 7.

Figure 9: Details of related sea surface features in SAR and SeaWiFS data including the radar backscatter level in each area.

Figure 10: ECMWF reanalysis wind fields during the 4th of May
(Please notice the different colour scales for the wind speed).

R.Sat.12.May.00 06:00z Denmark W.coast.

Figure 11: Radarsat ScanSAR image (06:00 UTC) with corresponding AVHRR SST image (14:55 UTC).
ECMWF wind field from time of Radarsat image (06 UTC) on May 12th, 2000.

Oil pollution and Surface Film

During the last few decades the pollution of the world's oceans has become a matter of increasing international concern. One source of marine pollution is shipping and maritime activities in general. In tonnage terms, the most important pollutant resulting from shipping operations is oil. The best known cause of oil pollution is that arising from tanker accidents. Although this contributes a comparatively small percentage of the total oil entering the sea in a year, the consequences of an accident can be disastrous to the immediate area, particularly if the ship involved is a large one and the accident occurs close to the coast. The wrecks of *Erica* (in 2000) and *Prestige* (in 2002) are examples, where extensive oceanic and coastal waters were contaminated.

An oil spill is discharge of any type of oil (raw oil, fuel, etc.) from a platform installation, a land terminal, a drilling vessel or another kind of vessel. Large amounts of oil can give a significant reduction of the backscatter in a satellite radar (SAR) image. The amount of oil being released into the sea by an accidental oil spill can be very large, and may have serious impact on the surroundings and environment depending on amongst others the meteorological conditions, season and location.

A “famous” example of an Envisat ASAR image of an oil spill is shown in Figure 12 c) from November 2002. This was taken during the *Prestige* tanker accident off the Spanish coast (see map in Figure 12 a) and was in fact one of the first ASAR images to be produced by the newly launched satellite. The image shows the oil drifting in two branches from the sinking ship wreck, possibly due to surface and subsurface discharge. At this time the wind speed was moderate to high and westerly and therefore the oil drifted to the shore and caused massive pollution of the Spanish and French Atlantic coast. The second image (Figure 12 d) is from the Bay of Biscay a month later. The slicks in the open sea are believed (not confirmed) to be oil. More information on the accident and many examples of oil in SAR images is available from http://earth.esa.int/ew/oil_slicks/galicia_sp_02/. This website follows the disaster from space from the time of the accident in November 2002 to April 2003 where oil slicks still were found in the area.

The amount of oil released during the tow and break-up of the tanker were estimated to 12,000 to 17,000 m³; further 5,000 to 10,000 m³ were released during the descent and hitting the sea floor and until end of January 2003, about 3,000 to 6,000 m³ leaked out every day¹. The oil has been characterized as IFO-650 (Daling et al., 2003): a very heavy fuel oil (burner oil) with a viscosity of 650 cSt at 50°C and a density of 0.995 kg/l. It was also found that it increased its viscosity during the months in the 15 deg. water. Under Norwegian conditions (5°C sea water in winter) the viscosity would have been even higher. A high viscosity of the oil leads to very efficient dampening of the Bragg waves (short wind generated waves).

Oil slicks on the sea surface can be of many different types. The crude oil from different regions in the world is very different in terms of density and viscosity. In refineries the oil is separated into everything from the light gasoline over diesel and lubricate oils to the rest products that are used for making plastic. All of these oil types can be spilled in the region. Classification is done according to how heavy the oil is (Table 1). The light oils evaporate quickly and an oil slick consisting of light oil will only cause dampening of the sea at low to moderate wind speeds. The denser oil types will give a clear dampening of the short gravity

¹Source: http://www.poseidon.ncmr.gr/mersea_metno/

waves even at moderate wind speeds. The oil properties are also sensitive to the sea temperature, such that at high temperatures they are lighter than at low temperatures. In the subsections below different sources of oil spill and surfactants in the ocean are described. In principle it is not possible to distinguish different oil types and their sources from the current SAR images. It must also be strongly emphasised that a big overlap between the signatures of e.g. light oil and natural film is expected, simply due to the fact that the two oils can have similar properties when it relates to dampening of Bragg waves and spreading and distribution on the sea surface. Successive images could be used to trace suspicious features and separate the man made slicks from natural slicks and in some cases reveal continuous release of oil.

Figure 12: The Prestige accident starting 16th November 2002 off the Atlantic coast of Spain. The accident happened close to the coast at (1) in the map but was towed offshore where it sank at (6). The tanker carried 67,000 tons of oil. The picture at the top right shows the tanker leaking oil and the small picture beside the map shows it as it breaks in two and sinks. At the bottom are two Envisat ASAR images from 17th November and 22nd December 2002. (Source: ESA and http://earth.esa.int/ew/oil_slicks/galicia_sp_02/.)

Produced water

Produced water is water that comes from the reservoir together with the oil during production. Water produced in offshore facilities often times is disposed of "overboard". In order to do

this, oil and gas producers must adhere to strict regulations requiring water purification and removal of organic and inorganic materials from the water that could cause damage the environment and local eco-systems. Even though this water is separated from the oil and cleaned before being released into the sea, it will still contain traces of oil and process chemicals. With a sufficient amount of oil-based substances, produced water can give slick signatures in SAR images. The amount of produced water released on the Norwegian shelf is expected to increase for some years before it will start to decrease. On the British shelf it has already started to decrease as a result of several oil fields are being closed down (SFT 2003, pp. 17).

Slicks caused by produced water can be very similar in shape and texture to slicks caused by oil spill. In low to moderate wind conditions it is difficult to distinguish between the two types of slicks. As the wind increases >7-8 m/s a slick caused by produced water will have more diffuse edges and the slick may be broken up into several parts. As for oil spill, there is no way to estimate the amount of oil in the slick based on SAR data alone.

Table 1: Oil classifications. From Lenting and Prat (2000).

Group	Specific gravity	Description and examples
I	< 0.8	Light distillates Maui and Kapuni condensate Gasoline blendstocks Motor spirit (RMS/PMS), Avgas Jet A1, kerosene
II	0.80 - 0.85	Middle distillates and light crudes Gas oils Light crudes
III	0.85 - 0.95	Medium – heavy crudes, fuel oils LFO Medium – heavy crudes
IV	0.95 - 1.00 or high pour point crudes	Heavy crudes and residues HFO Residues Fletcher blend, Maui F sands below pour point Lube oils and lube blendstocks
V	> 1.0	Very heavy fuel and bunker oils HBFO Bitumen

Water-based or oil-based drilling mud

Water-based or oil-based drilling mud is used when drilling wells. The Norwegian State Pollution Control Authority (SFT) regulates the use of drilling fluids/muds through discharge permits. Water based muds are tested under OSPAR formats for bio-accumulation potential and bio-degradability and given a discharge permit if judged to be environmentally friendly. Synthetic muds are similarly evaluated and can be given a discharge permit according to their properties, but at present discharge of SBMs are not allowed north of the 62nd parallel. All oil-based muds are injected or taken to shore for treatment. The discharge of solids containing more than 1% oil, by weight, is forbidden - whether the drilling fluid is water-, oil- or synthetic-based (Source: <http://www.offshore-environment.com>). The water based mud may cause slick signatures in a SAR image when released into the sea.

Drain Water

Drain water is rainwater and other water (e.g. for washing the platform decks), which is collected through an open drain system on a oil platform. The drain water also goes through a cleaning process before it is released into the sea, but it may still contain traces of oil. Thus, it may be visible as a dark feature in a SAR image.

Ballast water with traces of oil

The introduction of invasive marine species into new environments by ships' ballast water, attached to ships' hulls and via other vectors has been identified as one of the greatest threats to the world's oceans. Shipping moves over 80% of the world's commodities and transfers approximately 3 to 5 billion tonnes of ballast water internationally each year. A similar volume may also be transferred domestically within countries and regions each year. Ballast water is absolutely essential to the safe and efficient operation of modern shipping, providing balance and stability to un-laden ships. However, it may also pose a serious ecological, economic and health threat. (Source: <http://globallast.imo.org>).

Apart from the serious risk of ballast water containing foreign biological species (e.g. causing harmful algae blooms) ballast water can contain traces of oil. For tankers without separate ballast tanks, this water may contain traces of oil from the previous oil cargo. Thus, it may cause slick signatures in a SAR image, depending on the remaining amount of oil after the cleaning process.

Ballast water with oil is often released while the ship is moving and causes long slicks after the ship. In calm weather the slick can stay for many hours and parts of it can be moved with the currents. The slick will often be seen in connection with a ship, which is depicted as bright points in a SAR image.

Gas Oil

Crude oil can be broken down in different fractions, reaching from gasoline to wax or what is used for making plastics. Gas oil is one of these fractions. The gas oil fraction is a heavy, relatively slow burning, non-volatile fuel, or it is frequently used as a light lubricating oil. This fraction can be used either as a fuel or as an oil. If the gas oil fraction is hydroprocessed, it can be made into white oil (sewing machine oil) or high quality oils for use in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals.

Natural Oil slicks

Biological film may cause natural slicks at the water surface. These are mainly caused by fish oil or by phytoplankton.

Fish Oil

Vegetable and animal oils represent a large amount of solids and liquids carried by ships. They are classified as MARPOL category D (substances virtually non-toxic to aquatic life), authorising, according to the MARPOL 73/78 Convention (http://www.londonconvention.org/marpol_73.htm), the dumping of water and residue of tanks washed on board ships. Amongst the accidents involving the spillage of vegetable oils at sea, two cases concerning the area of responsibility set down in the Bonn Agreement took

place: the *Kimya* shipwreck which, through sunflower oil, caused wide pollution in Wales in 1991, and the collision of the *Allegra* which resulted in a spillage of 900 tons of palm nut oil in the Channel in 1997. Most common vegetable oils will remain liquid when spilled in the sea as they have a melting point below 0° C. As fish oil has a melting point between 9 and 45°C, the physical state of the spilled product (solid or liquid) will depend on the temperature of the water (Source: http://www.bonnagreement.org/eng/html/counter-pollution_manual/Chapter25.htm)

It happens that trawlers discharge fish oil during fishing. If the concentration of fish oil is high and the sea temperature is low, the signature of the slicks may be similar to that of man-made slicks. At high temperatures, wind may be able to spread the oil quickly, while at low temperatures the fish oil will be thicker and might behave as some man made oil types. Mackerel and herring are fish types with high level of oil, in particular in the autumn. It is possible that fishing these in large amounts can lead to slicks of fish oil on the sea surface. However this is not documented at present. The season for Mackerel is April to November. Different Herring stocks have season at different times of year.

Algae blooms and surfactants

Fish and several plankton species may secrete organic substances of chemical, physiochemical and biological characteristics in the upper ocean. Under certain oceanographic and meteorological conditions, such substances can be transported to the surface by rising bubbles, convection, upwelling and diffusion. When reaching the surface these surfactant molecules tend to be absorbed at the air-water interface and remain there as a microlayer material. Accumulation may take place in regions of high biological activity, i.e. in coastal regions, in regions of upwelling, and along current boundaries. In situations with weak ocean currents and low to moderate wind, these layers can cover extensive ocean areas up to several hundred square kilometers. Natural film is only created when biological activity in the ocean is high, and is therefore generally limited to the spring, summer and autumn seasons. Since the layer is thin, and the organic substances are elastic, both current and wind will influence it and often patterns such as eddies and current fronts are depicted. Thus natural film appears as large areas, dark or full of eddies depicted by low and higher backscatter looking very chaotic. In such cases, dark features that are not following the natural shapes are not due to the natural film.

The layer of natural film is only able to dampen the short waves generated at low wind speed. At low wind speed the radar backscatter in the areas where the film is not present will also be low. The contrast between the high and low backscatter is therefore not very high for natural slicks. At shallow incidence angles, regions with natural film may appear dark due to the low wind speed. The combination of low wind speed and shallow incidence angles (outer 1/3 of the Wide Swath Mode and ScanSAR mode) are conditions that are not suited for oil spill detection.

A special case is algae blooms. Under the right conditions, a specific type of algae (e.g. *chatonnella*, cyanobacteria, flagellate, coccolithophorid etc.) can bloom up in large amounts in the North and Baltic Seas. During high-biomass blooms near the surface, the waste products are able to cause dampening of the Bragg waves. High biomass algae blooms are typically observed in the spring (late April - May) but algae blooms occur during most of the spring and summer from late Feb – early July, and again in August, and late September. Since some of these blooms are harmful to aquaculture or poisonous to humans they are supervised using optical satellite remote sensing such as on <http://HAB.nersc.no> (see Section 0). The

Algae Bloom Monitoring service of Norway (<http://algeinfo.imr.no/>) has monitoring stations along the coast and publish information about possible algae blooms every week.

Figure 13: Natural film on the surface depicting oceanic eddies. Their extent and presence may dominate significant parts of the ocean. Generally they are visible in radar images under low wind speed conditions.

Monitoring of Water Quality in Rivers– Some Examples

A literature review of applications of satellite EO data for studies of rivers and in land waters has been done focusing on monitoring of contaminants and on area extent of river flooding.

Time series of contaminants

Contaminants refer to any foreign or unwanted substances that are harmful to ecosystem and human health, as well as those that are deemed undesirable from an aesthetic standpoint. On the global scale contamination of ground and surface water poses the most significant health risk to humans, and there are many diseases resulting from exposures to poorly treated drinking water. Contaminants may be present in groundwater or surface water as a result of natural processes or through mechanisms of displacement and dispersal related to human activities. There are two types of contaminants – those of point and non-point (diffuse) sources. Point source originated from discrete sources whose inputs into aquatic systems can often be defined in spatially explicit manner. Non point sources, in contrast, originated from poorly defined, diffuse sources that typically occur over broad geographical scales. Many studies of contaminants in rivers using time series data applying different sampling methods, Canovas et al. (2007) investigated the hydrogeochemical characteristics of the Tinto and Odiel rivers in Spain. Collavini et al. (2005) studied pollutant loads from the drainage basin to the Venice Lagoon, Italy using data collected during the year 1999. Strauch et al. (2005) assessed the pollution of water protection areas and river banks along Elbe and Mulde rivers after the flood event in August 2002 using soil and vegetation sampling. Remote sensing data can be an important source of information for contaminant studying, their main area of uses are to identify and assess the impact of land use and land cover as well as land use management practices on water quality. Adu-Prah used Landsat 7 ETM⁺ to assess land use/land cover influence on water quality of streams in Coles Creek, Mississippi watershed. Wang Pei-juan (2004) developed a method to monitor and analyze the mineral environment, especially for water and vegetation, with aid of remote sensing images (Landsat), field spectral data and digital elevation model. Macklin et al. (2006) outlined a geomorphological approach to the management of rivers contaminated by metals, four emerging themes are highlighted, one them, new developments in isotopic fingerprinting, remote sensing and numerical modelling for identifying the sources of contaminant metals and for mapping spatial distribution of contaminant in river channels and floodplain.

Area extent of flooding

Floods are the major disaster affecting many countries in the world year after year. It is an inevitable natural phenomenon occurring from time to time in all rivers and natural drainage systems that is not only damages the lives, natural resources and environment but also loss of economy and health. Floods can result from disruption to natural or manmade dams, catastrophic melting of ice and snow, rain, river ice jams and/or excessive runoff in the spring. For flood prediction, monitoring and measurement accurate information of the extent of the water bodies is important. This information is often difficult to produce using traditional survey techniques because water bodies can be fast moving as in floods, tides, and storm surges or may be inaccessible.

Remote sensing technology have been used to study flooding for the last two decades, they used to measure and monitor the surface extent of the flooded area, to efficient target rescue efforts and to provide quantifiable estimate of the amount of land and infrastructure affected. Some of the advantages of remote sensing include its near-global and frequent repeat coverage of large spatial extent (e.g., 1km-AVHRR, and 25km-QuickSCAT / RadarSat and twice-daily repeat MODIS and once per 16 days Landsat, respectively. Main disadvantage have been cloud cover for the optical sensors and poor sensor spatial resolution in many cases (e.g. 250 metre - MODIS).

There are two main steps involved in flood mapping using remote sensing data; first to identify water vs. non-water areas before and during the flood event, respectively, then to compare the areas classified as water or non-water before, during and after the flood event to determine which areas flooded (Figure 14). Once water vs. non-water areas on both dates (before and during/after a flood) are made, one can determine that an area is flooded or not. Combining this information with high resolution digital elevation models will allow for estimation of the additional river flux (volume) due to the flooding.

Figure 14: Before and After Landsat Imagery for the Mississippi Flood of 1997(Photo Courtesy of Space Imaging EOSAT) (<http://gis2.esri.com/library/userconf/proc02/pap0490/p0490.htm>).

A production line to retrieval of Water Quality Parameters from OC data

Commonly satellite Earth Observation data are organized in at least 3 Levels, due to their level of processing and aggregation; Level-1; the sensor based engineering unit, Level-2; Geophysical retrieval of the parameter to be mapped and Level-3; Time and space binning of the geophysical quantities.

A production line for EO data acquisition, processing, products generation, and dissemination (web map server) for a given study area is suggested, where level-2 data are used to generate higher level information for the users. The satellite based water quality information is being ingested into the service in near real-time on “daily” basis accessing data sources in operation by the space agencies. In this context the European Space Agency ground segment for the Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS). . The products are generated according to the NERSC specific processing chain illustrated in Figure 15, including three major tasks;

Task 1: Access to and acquisition of EO Level-2 data products

Task 2: Production Processing line and Statistical binning of EO data products

Task 3: Data Integration, Analysis and Assessment/Visualization

	Steps	Data format	Shell script
Download	MERIS on ESA ftp (Rolling archives)	N1	Launch scripts for the various steps ↓
	Data download		
	MERIS on NERSC server	N1	
Processing	Map re-projection		
	MERIS	DIM	
	NERSC algorithm (BOREALI) processing		
	MERIS	DIM +IMG	
	Post-processing (Matlab)		
Visualisation	Concentration distribution maps +transect extracts (daily, weekly, monthly)	JPG TIFF	
	Web visualisation (php)		
	Data on the screen for end user	HTML	

Figure 15 The NERSC processing chain for generation of various MERIS based ocean products for use in near real-time or off-line applications.

Task 1 – Access to EO Data (Level-1/2)

Pending on the commercial or scientific nature of the monitoring access to satellite EO data are established through the public or private sources of Level-1B or Level-2 satellite EO data supply. For scientific purposes the EO data can be made available at no or reproduction costs, preferably distributed in NRT through the ESA Envisat ftp-rolling archive at ESRIN or as an back up off-line shipped via other data media (CD-ROM) to the project partner. In the context

of GMES such data will be available through the Marine Core Services to be established under FP7 from 2008 (for European waters). The ftp-rolling archive option is currently in operation and a script to down-load the MERIS data is initiated less than 12 hours after the satellite passing the SAM area, i.e. during the following night after the satellite overpass.

Task 2: Production Line for EO Products Processing (Level 2) and Statistical Binning (Level 3)

The production line for the geographical sub-sampling and presentation of the EO data products is based on daily generation of merged seven days binned products as well as monthly binning of the regional data once per calendar month for all derived parameters. The products are based on “standard” ESA MERIS RR (1 km) and RR (300 meter) data products for each of the proposed parameters. The service production line is under implementation, however still for internal use, evaluation and quality control located at <http://hab.nersc.no/archive.php>.

Figure 16: Screen dump of a selection of 1-day and 7-days binned information products for a 3-days period in May 2006. Here shown is the ESA chlorophyll-a case 1 (algal_1), the NERSC/NIERSC Chl-a (Imchl) and the MODIS SST (sst) products, delivered under both MarCoast services S3 and S4. The image examples are binned for respectively 1-day and 7-days periods. The user can interactively select the information products, their binning period (1-, 7-days or monthly) and time period for display. Here the data are shown for the baseline MarCoast SLA-agreed area of coverage i.e. “the North Sea”. The user can download the images in GeoTIFF, KML for Google or MatLab (password access) formats for own further processing. Some additional geographical areas of coverage have been introduced during 2006.

This “production line” is based on the experience with regular monitoring of algal blooms in Norwegian waters since 1998 to present, using SeaWiFS, MODIS and MERIS EO data sources, and as disseminated through <http://HAB.nersc.no>, which is an on-going GMES MarCoast water quality and harmful algae bloom monitoring service for northern European waters. Processed EO data products are generated as image files for web-display (GeoTIFF), in KML format for use in GoogleEarth (Figure 17 here shown for Central American waters) and as data files (e.g. MatLab) for further processing and generation of derived products.

Figure 17: The 7-days merged MERIS RR algal_1 (Chlorophyll-a) product for February 13th 2007, displayed using GoogleEarth. Clouds are in grey and a scale bare will be included on the image.

Task 3: Data Integration, Analysis and Assessment

A web-map server, based on the EU DISMAR project technology (DISPRO-2²) can be implemented in order to be able to merge and integrate the environmental information provided by WARMER (EO products and buy data) as well as by the regional users (other field data and information).

² Sandven, S., T. Hamre, B. Hackett, K. Sørensen, N. Robbe, F. Ziemer, A. Bogdanov, G. Gemelli, F. Nirchio, F. Cauneau, É. Ô Tuama, S. Groom, F. Parthiot, P. Trivero, J. Populus, A. Folkestad, L. H. Pettersson, M. Cysewski, K. Lewis, J.-F. Le Roux, J. Høkedal, J. Karud, W. Biamino (2005). DISMAR Final Report. NERSC Technical Report No. 266. http://www.nersc.no/Projects/dismar/Reports/D11_Final_Report_DISMAR.pdf

The DISPRO prototype implements an OGC Web Map Service (WMS) system [OGC04]. The DISPRO prototype consists of a set of distributed data nodes, each providing an OGC WMS interface, and a portal that communicates with the nodes and provides various client applications such as a map viewer, profiler, and metadata catalogue. The implementation of the DISPRO system uses Java and XML technologies, with the Open Source University of Minnesota (UMN) MapServer, running as a CGI application under the Apache web server providing the core web GIS client and OGC WMS (both client and server) functionality. The main components of DISPRO are the catalogue, the profiler, and the web-GIS. In brief, the catalogue keeps track of all products available through the providers' data nodes, the profiler allows users to tailor the system to deliver specific types of products for their area of interest, and the web GIS allows the user to view the map layers in the particular geographic bounding box and map projection previously selected using the profiler form. The DISPRO GIS browser client interface (Figure 18) provides basic functions expected of a thin client such as selection/deselection of layers, drag-select zoom box, panning, zooming and centring, and reference map area and scalebar. It consists of four main areas: the map area, the layer list, the map controls, and the information panel.

Figure 18: The DISPRO GIS client interface: a wind forecast is overlaid on a satellite chlorophyll-a image in the North Sea/Skagerrak area – to be used as a template for implementation in the WARMER project.

Selected Airborne Remote Sensing Systems

AIRCRAFT OBSERVATION OF OIL SPILLS – THE GERMAN SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

Introduction

The multispectral remote sensing data from the Do228 LM57+01 surveillance aircraft operated by Optimare are used for oil spill monitoring in German coastal waters. This aircraft is one of the two German maritime surveillance aircraft which are operated by the 3rd Naval Air Wing on behalf of the German Ministry of Transport (Figure 19) (Sandven et al., 2003).

Figure 19: German maritime surveillance aircraft Do 228 LM57+01 with its remote sensing instrumentation (www.optimare.de).

Airborne data are collected during routine operations over the North and the Baltic sea and also during dedicated experiments and campaigns. Optimare provides processing, analysis and archiving of airborne data from completed flight missions. Figure 20 shows the data processing diagram at Optimare.

The sensors and data types provided by the German surveillance aircraft are described in the following sections.

Figure 20: The processing steps for airborne data at Optimare.

Side Looking Airborne Radar (SLAR)

Long range surveillance is carried out with a Side Looking Airborne Radar (SLAR) which may be operated in three different modes, allowing the monitoring of sea areas up to 40 km each side of the aircraft, or 80 km to the left or right. Radar pulses are sent to both sides of the aircraft and reflected from ships or from waves on the sea surface. In the case of oil on water the backscatter from the sea surface is reduced resulting in dark areas within the radar image. The radar image contains ambiguities in the case of low wind areas where there are no waves or where natural films on the surface also dampen the sea surface roughness. These ambiguities make it necessary to further investigate each detected possible oil slick by the help of near range sensors.

Infrared/Ultraviolet Line Scanner (IR/UV)

The IR/UV scanner operates in an altitude of 300m resulting in a swath width of approximately 500 m. The UV channel, operating between 320 and 380 nm, detects the reflected sunlight from the water surface. Very thin oil films can be investigated with a film thickness down to 0.1 microns. Depending on sunlight this sensor is restricted to daylight and good visibility conditions. The IR channel detects the thermal emission from the sea surface in the spectral region from 8 to 12 microns. Due to the fact that oil has a lower emissivity than water thin oil layers usually appear colder than the surrounding water surface. But it is well known that this effect may not be used for quantitative investigation because oil spills with a thickness of more than 0.5 mm tend to absorb much sunlight and therefore appear warmer than the water, especially on sunny days. Nevertheless, the IR detector may be operated during day and night time although the contrast between water and oil may completely change.

Imaging Airborne Laser Fluorosensor (IALFS)

The IAFLS is one of the most complex and quantitatively measuring remote sensing instruments operated on the aircraft and is designed with two high energy pulse lasers in the UV at 308 nm and 383 nm. The stimulated fluorescence as well as the scattering of the laser light at the water surface and within the water column are detected with a 20 cm telescope and

then spectrally separated into 12 detection channels. Operational altitude is between 100 and 300 m resulting in a surface swath width of 150 to 450m, utilizing a conical scanner. The main features of the sensors are: estimation of oil film thickness between 0.1 and 10 microns, calculation of the oil volume on the water surface, identification and classification of the oil through spectral signature, discrimination between natural and mineral oil films and detection of oil below the water surface. In addition, the laser fluorosensor may be used for hydrographic measurements to evaluate the distribution of Gelbstoff (CDOM), identify hydrographic fronts by determining the water attenuation coefficients or to investigate algae blooms by measuring the chlorophyll fluorescence.

Microwave Radiometer (MWR)

The MWR is the second complex remote sensing instrument that enables quantitative assessments of detected oil spills. But whereas the laser fluorosensor has been developed for thin oil films the microwave radiometer has been designed to evaluate oil films between 50 microns and 5 mm. The detection of the radiant emission from the sea surface and oil spills in the frequencies 18.7, 36.5 and 89 GHz allow the rapid investigation of large amounts of oil, for example resulting from accidents. As a rule of thumb 90 percent of the oil is concentrated in 10 percent of the total area covered. It is therefore the purpose of airborne support operations to guide combat ships exactly to this highly contaminated region within a spill, where the ship's captain cannot identify thicker areas from his position on the bridge. As a scanning sensor the swath width of about 470 m at a flight altitude of 300 m has been designed to result in the same width like the IR/UV line scanner allowing an easy comparison of images. For calibration and improvement of data evaluation a zenith radiometer is installed on top of the aircraft enabling operation of the instrument even during cloudy situations with rain.

Data Analysis

After converting the raw data, all the sensor data except IALFS data are available as binary coded image data. The (12-channel) IALFS data is available as ASCII data after conversion and can be converted into image data by data gridding. MWR and IALFS data have, especially, to be corrected for further use.

EXAMPLES OF SENSOR DATA

In the following examples the near range data that were collected during the NOFO exercise in 1996 (Norway) are presented. During this mission all the near range sensors (IRUV/IALFS/MWR) were used.

IR/UV:

The IR image (Figure 21, left) shows the oil spill with areas which appear to be colder (due to the fact that oil has a lower emissivity than water) and with a hot zone in the centre of the oil spill which arises from the fact that the surface of the thick part of the spill is far from thermal equilibrium with the water surface due to solar heating. The UV image (Figure 21, right) reveals the total extent of the oil spill.

Figure 21: IR image (left) and UV image (right)

Figure 22: Microwave signatures from the three MWR channels (18.7, 36.5 and 89 GHz)

MWR:

Figure 22 shows the (post processed) signatures of the oil spill detected by the 3-channel Microwave Radiometer. All the three MWR images corresponding to the three detection frequencies 18.7, 36.5 and 89 GHz show the thick part of the oil spill. Quantitative analysis was not carried out in this case.

IALFS:

Figure 23 shows the images that were derived from the laser fluorosensor data and which correspond to the 12 detection channels of the IALFS. The images were calculated by a gridding algorithm based on Delaunay triangulation of the data. The data were acquired using excitation pulses at 308 nm. As it can be seen from the spectral signatures the channel at 344 nm shows a reduction of the signal inside of the oil spill (transition from red to blue). This is caused by the strong light absorption of the oil which in turn results in a suppression of the water Raman signal. Furthermore, the (normalized) fluorescence signatures of the other channels are shown. A classification of the oil pollution can be carried out on the basis of the IALFS data and a spatially resolved thickness estimate can be calculated from the suppression of the water Raman signal at 344 nm.

SLAR:

The SLAR image shown in Figure 24 was not acquired during NOFO'96 exercise but during a flight mission in 1994. It clarifies the principle of oil spill detection using a Side looking Airborne Radar. The two yellow arrows in the SLAR image point at dark patches caused by oil spills due to the reduction of the sea surface roughness.

More information about the airborne system provided by Optimare can be obtained at http://www.optimare.de/start_eng.html.

EXAMPLES FROM THE RUSSIAN AIRBORNE LIDAR SYSTEM

Introduction

The surveillance aircraft “Arktika” is operated by PINRO in Murmansk and is used for mapping ocean surface processes in the Barents and Norwegian Seas using a LIDAR system (*LI*ght *D*etection *A*nd *R*anging), Infrared Radiometer, Infrared Scanner, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and Microwave Radiometer (Zabavnikov, pers.comm.). Technical description of the aircraft and the sensors are presented in Annex 2.

Operating the airborne instruments onboard the “Arktika”

The LIDAR instrument, denoted PAL-1, has been installed and used onboard the two engine aircraft “Arktika” for surveillance of the sea surface (Figure 25). The LIDAR transmitting and receiving unit is placed in the photo-camera hatch closed by flat illuminator made of optical glass. The PAL-1 is important to map the surface layer of the ocean, since the PAL-1 signal penetration depth in the Norwegian Sea can reach 45 meters. The penetration depth depends on sea water transparency.

During airborne surveillance flights the LIDAR is used in combination with Microwave and Infrared Radiometer sensors (MWR, IR), including Infrared scanning, digital photo- and video surveys, and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). “Arktika” uses satellite navigation system – GPS and onboard computing system for processing the data (OCS). The aircraft is equipped with four blisters that allow observers to register fish schools, plankton strips, hydrodynamics effects and phenomena on sea surface, including carrying out observation on marine mammals and sea birds.

Figure 25: The AN-26 “Arktika” aircraft operated by PINRO.

The LIDAR observations are most effective and reliable at flight altitude of 150-200 m and average speed about 85 m/s. Surface waves should not exceed a maximum wave height of 4 m and a mean wave height of 1.5 m. The PAL-1 data is processed in two stages: (1) onboard of “Arktika”, in the real time and (2) post-processing after each flight, when more detailed

analysis is made and the remote sensing data are interpreted. The results of the LIDAR (PAL-1) processing provide the following information presented in GIS format:

- transparency;
- values of chlorophyll “a” fluorescence on sea surface;
- data about pycnocline depth;
- data about positions of area with high level of subsurface plankton concentration.

Results from the “Arktika” flights are shown in the following figures.

Figure 26. Coastal mapping using photographs and IR images

Figure 27: Profile of bathymetry from LIDAR data in the Svalbard region.

Figure 28: Example of temperature front from the IR scanner.

Figure 29: SAR observation of oil spill, shown as dark spots in the images

Summary and Conclusions

Discussion and Conclusions

The WARMER project is established under the EC IST portfolio of FP6 projects supporting the EC implementation of Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES).

Accordingly, integrated use of satellite Earth observation data is one important and challenging component of the project.

Aquatic environmental information is acquired at different spatial and temporal scales and shall in WARMER be systemized, combined and used in monitoring and in emergency response situations. The following demonstration scenario conditions apply to the challenges of the project:

- Integrated use of innovative buoy and (satellite) Earth observation monitoring technologies
- Detection and monitoring of hazardous and low concentration water pollution contaminants
- Local to regional scale monitoring and area of impact
- Emergency deployment and response
- Near real-time operations and analysis
- Advanced information technologies for data communication, assembly and integration
- Integrated analysis for monitoring and in an emergency response phase
- Efficient use of information in decision-making and management of crisis events
- Meeting information needs at high-level directives, based on detailed low-level measurements.

Accordingly the environmental measurements made at a lower level should be used and transferred to higher-level information applicable at decision-making at policy level (see Figure 30).

Figure 30 Sketch of the levels of information needs and scales making information from low level measurements to decision making at high level policies.

The WARMER project has developed and implemented advanced sensor technology for high accuracy measurements of a range of "water quality" parameters using innovative sensor

technologies. The buoy observations are typically made at high temporal frequency and at one geographical location (or a few locations), i.e. with coarse spatial resolution at frequent time intervals of observations. Several of the sensors developed will measure environmental contaminants present in the natural environment detectable at very low concentrations, however in sufficient quantities and concentrations to be of a high risk factor for human health and environmental safety (see Deliverables D.1 to D.4). The detection level of the sensors for several of the in water components is in the low range of concentrations - at $\mu\text{g/l}$ level. Several of the chemical compounds does not have other distinct attributes allowing indirect detection using e.g. remote sensing sensors – such as water discoloration colour (applies for e.g. phytoplankton, sediments and dissolved organic matter) or surface film forming attributes (applies for e.g. crude oil or biological surfactants).

In this report we have presented relevant satellite Earth observation technologies and applications related to the targets to be monitored by the buoy system to be developed and used within WARMER. Few of the actual parameters measured by the WARMER buoy system are directly mapped directly by any of the existing (and planned) satellite Earth observation sensors. Accordingly, we suggest an integrated monitoring approach using a facet of optical, infrared and microwave satellite Earth observation sensors for mapping of the WARMER demonstration areas. The integrated use of these information sources will then form the basis for the assessment of the emergency /environmental situation. The proposed suit of EO sensors includes the European Space Agency Envisat sensors - MERIS FR (Medium resolution Imaging Spectrometer – Full Resolution), AATSR (Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer), and ASAR (Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar Image mode). Similar EO sensor systems are in operation by other space agencies, e.g. NASA (MODIS Aqua and Terra) and Canada (Radarsat).

This approach will provide the WARMER project with regional and local information about the aquatic ecosystem system that will be integrated and used in connection with the buoy monitoring. Near real-time access to this satellite information and integration of this with the *in situ* observations are assured. The range of environmental parameters derived from and the spatial resolution of these satellite Earth observations systems introduce some limitations in their applications in conjunction with the WARMER buoy system. These types of satellite observations are provided at a medium spatial resolution (some 100s of meters) for the surface parameters, however only with repeated updates at the best every one to three days. Accordingly, detailed monitoring of e.g. rivers and near shore locations will require use of higher resolution Earth observation sensors (≈ 10 's meters level), however such EO sensors mainly do not meet the requirements with frequent spatial coverage nor wrt. near real-time availability of the data.

Accordingly it is suggested that the project demonstrations will take place at coastal locations in which one may expect gradients in the level of contaminants are used for the assessment of the project development. Access to use of airborne system will be evaluated, however their use may cause significant budget constraints and a location with on going airborne survey may be suggested.

In addition the information should be supplemented with higher spatial resolution satellite EO sensors information from optical sensors (see Annex to report), such as the Ikonos sensor. However, these data are generally not available with frequent coverage for a given location and their terms of near real-time access are not usually good.

For the above core configuration of EO sensors the space agencies have also plans for a continuation of missions, e.g. the European (ESA/EU) Sentinel missions (primarily no. 1 and 3 for the ocean applications), assuring availability of this type of data also for the future.

These sensors and mission also provides regular spatial coverage of most European waters typically at intervals between 1 to 3 days. Some of these future missions will be operated with two or more similar satellites, improving the temporal coverage.

Both *in situ* buoy and satellite Earth observation information should be accessible from the same software platform for the users. Accordingly a web-based GIS system (Web-map system is recommended. The system for this integration should be based on the web-based DISPRO system prototype (Section 0) developed under the EC IST DISMAR project. The DISPRO SW has been exchanged with University of Aberdeen.

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Annex 1 – Descriptions of Selected Sensor Systems for Monitoring of Water Quality

AATSR - SST

Sensor Name	The Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer	
Operating Agency	European Space Agency (ESA)	
Applications	Ocean and Coast (Sea Surface Temperature) Atmosphere (Atmospheric chemistry (Trace Gases), Clouds) Land (Vegetation)	
Derived WQ Parameters	Sea Surface Temperature (SST)	
Spectral resolution	VIS - NIR: 0.555, 0.659, 0.865 micrometers, SWIR: 1.6 micrometers, MWIR: 3.7 micrometers, TIR: 10.85, 12 micrometers	
Temporal revisit	1 to 3 days	
Spatial resolution	IR ocean channels: 1km x 1km, Visible land channels: 1km x 1km	
Swath coverage	500 km	
Example application	<p>This AATSR view of the Bay of Biscay shows sea surface temperature (SST) and was acquired 15 September 2003.</p>	
Availability	Operational	
Data costs	Free of charge	
Data access	http://www.envisat.esa.int/resources/catalogues/ ENVISAT data for commercial or operational use (Category 2) http://www.eurimage.com http://www.spotimage.com	

Aster

Sensor Name	Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER)
Operating Agency	The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), Japan's Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) and Japan's Earth Remote

	Sensing Data Analysis Centre (ERSDAC).	
Applications	Glaciology, Hydrology, Urban change, Volcanology, Evapotranspiration / Surface Fluxes	
Derived WQ Parameters	Water clarity and circulation	
Spectral resolution	3 bands VNIR (0.52-0.60, 0.63-0.69, 0.76-0.86) 6 bands SWIR (1.6-1.7, 2.145-2.185, 2.185-2.225, 2.235-2.285, 2.295-2.365, 2.360-2.430) 5 band TIR (8.125-8.475, 8.475-8.825, 8.925-9.275, 10.25-10.95, 10.95-11.65)	
Temporal revisit	16 days	
Spatial resolution	VNIR 15m, SWIR 30 and TIR 90m.	
Swath coverage	60km	
Example application	<p>The image shows an at-sensor brightness temperature image for Lake Tahoe (33 km long, 18 km wide) from ASTER data acquired at night on June 3rd 2001 . Examination of the image indicates a strong cold plume of water originating in the west, traveling across the lake to the east shore, then spreading north and south. The cold plume of water is the result of a wind-induced upwelling event in west. The upwelling is induced by strong, persistent winds from the southwest which move the surface water to the east allowing the deep cold water in the west to upwell. The cold water is nutrient rich compared with the warmer surface waters which have been depleted of nutrients. The temperature images from ASTER can be used to map these nutrient pathways which help explain the distribution of organic matter and fine sediments around the lake.</p> <p>http://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/content/03_data/05_Application_Examples/hydrology/default.htm</p>	
Availability	Operational/ on demand	
Data costs	85 US\$ per scene	
Data access	http://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/ http://glovis.usgs.gov/ http://edcimswww.cr.usgs.gov/pub/imswelcome/	

AVHRR - SST

Sensor Name	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometers (AVHRR).
Operating Agency	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Agency (NOAA).
Applications	Sea surface temperature and Sea Ice, Geology, Vegetation, Snow Cover, Fire Monitoring and Fuel Potential.
Derived WQ Parameters	Sea Surface Temperature (SST).
Spectral resolution	Band1 (0.58-0.68), Band2 (0.725-1.10), Band3 (3.55-3.93), Band4 (10.3-11.3), Band5 (11.5-12.5).
Temporal revisit	9 days at nadir

Spatial resolution	1.1km
Swath coverage	2399km
Example application	Monthly composites of Sea Surface Temperature (June 2006) from the NOAA18 AVHRR satellites are shown.
Availability	Operational
Data costs	
Data access	http://www.noaa.gov/index.html

Envisat ASAR

Sensor Name	An Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR)	
Operating Agency	European Space Agency (ESA)	
Applications	Ocean and Coast (Ocean Currents and Topography) Land (Landscape Topography) Snow and Ice (Snow and Ice).	
Derived WQ Parameters		
Spectral resolution	Microwave: C-band, with choice of 5 polarisation modes (VV, HH, VV/HH, HV/HH, or VH/VV)	
Temporal revisit		
Spatial resolution	Image, Wave and Alternating Polarisation modes: approx 30m x 30m. Wide Swath mode: approx 150m x 150m. Global Monitoring mode: approx 1000m x 1000m.	
Swath coverage	Image and alternating polarisation modes: up to 100km, Wave mode: 5km, Wide swath and global monitoring modes: 400km or more	
Example application	<p>These images, made by comparing radar images acquired before and after flooding, show the precise extent of the flooding in the Saone valley (France). It helps identifying the areas of highest risk to deploy rescue forces as well as allows developing more precise models to assess the potential risks and to take actions to prevent them. Photo: Sertit/ESA 2001</p>	
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs		
Data access	EOLI Web Site & ELOI Stand Alone http://envisat.eas.int/services/catalogues.html Rolling Archive Envisat Web File Server	

Ikonos

Sensor Name	Ikonos	
Operating Agency	GeoEye	
Applications	National Security, Regional & Local Governments, Air & Marine Mapping, Fishing & Oceanographic Mapping, Environmental & Environmental Monitoring, Weather and Commercial.	
Derived WQ Parameters		
Spectral resolution	Panchromatic, blue, green, red, near IR	
Temporal revisit	The revisit rate for IKONOS is 3 to 5 days off-nadir and 144 days for true-nadir.	
Spatial resolution	1m panchromatic (PAN), 4m multi-spectral (MS) & 1m pan-sharpened (PS)	
Swath coverage	11 km x 11 km (Single Scene)	
Example application	<p>The plume of the Culebrinas River is detected with an IKONOS image. The disturbance in the plume by the movement of boats can be clearly seen in this image.</p> <p>http://cacique.uprm.edu/gers/</p>	
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs	1m Panchromatic 22.50 US\$ per square kilometre. 1m colour 24.75 US\$ per square kilometre. 4m Multispectral 18 US\$ per square kilometre.	
Data access	http://www.geoeye.com/	

Landsat

Sensor Name	Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+)	
Operating Agency	The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).	
Applications	Agriculture, Forestry, and Range Resources, Land Use and Mapping, Geology, Water Resources, Coastal Resources.	
Derived WQ Parameters	Measurement of sediment and turbidity patterns, Tracing oil spills and pollutants	
Spectral resolution	<p>Eight spectral bands, including a pan and thermal band:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Band 1 Visible (0.45 – 0.52μm) 30m • Band 2 Visible (0.52 – 0.60μm) 30m • Band 3 Visible (0.63 – 0.69μm) 30m • Band 4 Near Infrared (NIR) (0.76 – 0.90μm) 30m • Band 5 NIR (1.55 – 1.75μm) 30m • Band 6 Thermal (10.40 – 12.50μm) 60 m Low Gain / High Gain • Band 7 Mid IR (2.08 – 2.35μm) 30m • Band 8 Panchromatic (PAN) (0.52 - 0.90μm) (15m) 	
Temporal revisit	233 orbits cycle every 16 days covers the complete globe (except for the highest polar latitudes).	
Spatial resolution	Band 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 7 30m band 6 60m band 8 15m	
Swath coverage	The scene coverage is 185 km wide \times 170 km high	
Example application	<p>An image from the Landsat-5 Thematic Mapper of the region around St. Louis Missouri on August 19, 1993, just after the peak of the Mississippi flood. http://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/</p>	
Availability	Operational	
Data costs	600 USD	
Data access	http://edcsns17.cr.usgs.gov/EarthExplorer/ , http://glovis.usgs.gov/ http://landsat.usgs.gov/project_facts/ground_assets/igs_network/index.php	

MERIS

Sensor Name	The Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer Instrument (MERIS)	
Operating Agency	European Space Agency (ESA)	
Applications	Ocean and Coast (Ocean Colour/Biology) Land (Vegetation) Atmosphere (Clouds, precipitation)	
Derived WQ Parameters	Suspended matter, Phytoplankton and Gelbstoff.	
Spectral resolution	VIS-NIR: 15 bands selectable across range: 390nm to 1040nm	
Temporal revisit	Global coverage every 3 days	
Spatial resolution	Ocean: 1040m x 1200m, Land & coast: 260m x 300m	
Swath coverage	1150km	
Example application	<p>The shallow northern section of the Caspian Sea is shown in this MERIS image. Variously classed as an enormous lake or the smallest full-fledged sea, the Caspian is the largest landlocked water body in the world, with a surface area of 371 000 square kilometres.</p> <p>http://www.esa.int/images/</p>	
Availability	Operational	
Data costs	Free of charge for research	
Data access	EOLI Web Site & ELOI Stand Alone http://envisat.eas.int/services/catalogues.html Rolling Archive Envisat Web File Server	

MODIS

Sensor Name	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS)	
Operating Agency	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)	
Applications	Land/Cloud/Aerosols Boundaries, Land/Cloud/Aerosols Properties, Ocean Colour/ Phytoplankton/ Biogeochemistry, Atmospheric Water Vapour, Surface/Cloud Temperature, Atmospheric Temperature, Cirrus Clouds Water Vapour, Cloud Properties, Ozone, Surface/Cloud Temperature and Cloud Top Altitude.	
Derived WQ Parameters	Ocean Colour/ Phytoplankton/ Biogeochemistry.	
Spectral resolution	36 spectral bands	
Temporal revisit	1 to 2 days.	
Spatial resolution	250m (bands 1-2) 500 m (bands 3-7) 1000 m (bands 8-36)	
Swath coverage	2330 km (cross track) by 10 km (along track at nadir).	
Example application	Norwegian, Phytoplankton	<p>http://satgeo.zum.de/satgeo/quicklooks/europa_ueberblick</p>
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs	Free of charge for research	
Data access	MODIS Level 1 data, geolocation, cloud mask, and Atmosphere products: http://ladsweb.nascom.nasa.gov/ MODIS land products: http://edcdaac.usgs.gov/dataproducts.asp MODIS cryosphere products: http://nsidc.org/daac/modis/index.html MODIS ocean colour and sea surface temperature products: http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/	

QuickBird

Sensor Name	QuickBird	
Operating Agency	DigitalGlobe	
Applications	Defence and Intelligence, Agriculture, Civil Government – Mapping, Wildfire Risk Assessment, Environmental, Forestry, Oil and Gas, Visualization & Simulation Products.	
Derived WQ Parameters		
Spectral resolution	Blue: 450 to 520 nm Green: 520 to 600 nm Red: 630 to 690 nm Near-IR: 760 to 900 nm.	
Temporal revisit	3-7 days depending on latitude	
Spatial resolution	Panchromatic: 60-centimeter, Multispectral: 2.4-meter	
Swath coverage	Single Area - 16.5 km x 16.5 km Strip - 16.5 km x 165 km	
Example application	<p>Text</p> <p>2.4-meter multispectral imagery, sharpened with 60-centimeter panchromatic, will be able to be used to identify and measure the surface dimensions of an oil spill</p>	<p>Figure</p>
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs	For panchromatic imagery is \$22.50 per square kilometre Multispectral products at \$25 per square kilometre	
Data access	http://www.digitalglobe.com/ http://www.eurimage.com/	

Radarsat

Sensor Name	Radarsat (SAR, ScanSar)	
Operating Agency	Canadian Space Agency (CSA)	
Applications	Ice Monitoring, Environmental Monitoring, Disasters management, Coastal water and open ocean, Hydrology, Geology, Agriculture, Forestry.	
Derived WQ Parameters		
Spectral resolution	Microwave: C-band (5.3), one polarisation mode HH	
Temporal revisit	24 days	
Spatial resolution	25-100m	
Swath coverage	100-170km	
Example application	<p>RADARSAT provides excellent land/water delineation. In this image, the forest cover and floodplain appear in tones of grey, while the water is distinctly black. The forests along the Amazon River and nearby lakes in Brazil experience seasonal flooding, and with the use of multi-temporal RADARSAT images, these areas can be mapped.</p> <p>http://www.space.gc.ca/asc/eng/satellites/radarsat1/hydrology.asp</p>	
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs	http://gs.mdacorporation.com/products/sensor/radarsat/rs1_price_us.asp	
Data access	http://www.space.gc.ca/asc/eng/satellites/radarsat1/order_data.asp	

SeaWiFS

Sensor Name	Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS).	
Operating Agency	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).	
Applications	Global ocean bio-optical properties.	
Derived WQ Parameters	Phytoplankton, sediments and dissolved organic matter	
Spectral resolution	8 optical bands (402- 885 nm)	
Temporal revisit	1 day	
Spatial resolution	1.1 km Local Area Coverage, 4.5 km Global Area Coverage	
Swath coverage	2,801 km Local Area Coverage (High Resolution Picture Transmission), 1,502 km Global Area Coverage	
Example application	<p>SeaWiFS has produced a image that shows algal blooms from plankton, in amounts related to chlorophyll count, in the Baltic Sea and Atlantic Ocean off Norway and adjacent countries.</p>	<p>http://rst.gsfc.nasa.gov/Sect14/Sect14_13.html</p>
Availability	Operational	
Data costs	Free of charge for research	
Data access	<p>Commercial Users: http://www.orbimage.com/prods/orbview_2.html NASA-Authorized Users (Receive SeaWiFS data freely from the Goddard Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC) http://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/dataset/SEAWIFS/. NASA-Authorized Ground Stations http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi/hrpt_station_info.pl</p>	

SPOT

Sensor Name	Satellites Pour l'Observation de la Terre or Earth-observing Satellites (SPOT)	
Operating Agency	Spot Image SA	
Applications	Defence, Intelligence, Security, Agriculture, Land planning and management, Energy, mines, Hazard management mitigation.	
Derived WQ Parameters		
Spectral resolution	Multispectral B1 0,50 - 0,59 μm 10m B2 0,61 - 0,68 μm 10m B3 0,79 - 0,89 μm 10m SWIR 1,58 - 1,75 μm 20m Monospectral PAN 0,51 - 0,73 μm 5m or 2.5m	
Temporal revisit	26 days	
Spatial resolution	Panchromatic mode 2.5m and 5m Multispectral mode 10m	
Swath coverage	60 km	
Example application	<p>Ebro river, Spain</p> <p>This extract is from a SPOT 5 10-metre-resolution scene acquired on 10 February 2003, three days after the Ebro river flooded.</p> <p>Flooding, which caused extensive damage to crops in the river valley, was the worst seen in Spain for 20 years.</p>	<p><small>SPOT 5 - 10m - Ebro - Spain - February 2003</small></p> <p>http://www.spotimage.fr/html/_167_240_941_250_.php</p>
Availability	Operational/On demand	
Data costs	Archive data: 20 m colour, 10m B&W 1900 euro, 5m colour, 2.5m B&W 5400 euro Programmed products: 20 m colour, 10m B&W 2700 euro, 5m colour, 2.5m B&W 6200 euro.	
Data access	http://www.spotimage.fr	

Annex 2. Technical specification of the Arktika aircraft.

AN-26 “ARKTIKA” (TWO ENGINES AIRCRAFT) TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Maximum flight distance (including flight to area of air surveys carrying out), km	to 5 400
Maximum flight duration (including flight to area of air surveys carrying out), hours	to 9
Flight altitude range (as possible), m	150-6000
Flight altitude range for effective air surveys, m	150-300
Flight speed range (dependent on wind speed and it direction), km/h	220-600
Flight speed range on altitude of effective air surveys (dependent on wind speed and it direction)	220-350
Numbers of seat for onboard observers and operators	8

MAIN SPECIFICATIONS OF AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING EQUIPMENTS

INFRARED RADIOMETER (IR-RADIOMETER) AIR-2. This equipment uses for sea surface temperature measurements along flight track under aircraft. The shortest distance between each sound is 2m.

<i>Main Technical Specifications</i>	<i>Values</i>
Spectral Range, micrometers	10...12
Measured Temperature Range, °□	-10...+40
Accuracy of Temperature Measurement, °□	0.15
Sensitivity, °□	0.08
Operating Temperature, °□	-20...+30

IR-SCANNER “MALAKHIT”. This equipment uses for collection data about thermal conditions on sea surface as thermal images. This equipment uses for identification of harp seals on sea ice in the first.

<i>Main Technical Specifications</i>	<i>Values</i>
Horizontal Resolution, mrad	1.55
Field of View (Swath), °	120
Sensitivity, °□	0.1
Maximum Scan Rate, Hz	125
Dynamic Range, bits	12

POLARIZABLE AVIATION RADAR (Light Detection And Ranging – LIDAR) – PAL-1. This equipment uses for sound of subsurface layers along flight track under aircraft. The shortest distance between each sound is 10m. Using this equipment allows to get data about transparency, sea surface chlorophyll “a” concentration, subsurface plankton concentration, and also this equipment can be used for fish school detection closely sea surface. The maximum depth of sounding pulse penetration is 40m for ocean water. Then water is more turbid then sounding pulse penetration as less.

<i>Main Technical Specifications</i>	<i>Values</i>
Radiation Wavelength, nm	1064; 532
Pulse Energy on Radiation Wavelength 532 nm, mJ	120 no more 10
Pulse Length on Level 0.5, ns	1...40
Repetition Rates, Hz	7
Operating Rate, Hz	1
Spot Diameter on Surface, m	polarizable
Radiation	dual
Receiver Polarization	linear
Receiver Type	10
Receiver Diameter, cm	8
Digitizer Resolution, bits	80
Sample Rate, MHz	

SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR SYSTEM (SAR). This equipment uses for getting information from sea surface as SAR image. In difference of previous remote sensing equipments it is all-weather system, which allows to get radar image in the swath dependent on flight altitude about hydrodynamics inhomogeneous (eddies, meanders, oceanographic fronts and so-on), organic pollutions (including oil spills) position and structure. Also it can be used very effectively for detection of fish schools closely sea surface. Usually onboard Russian research aircraft uses two RADAR with radiation wavelength 4 and 23cm (not simultaneously, sometimes one or other).

SAR-4 (radiation wavelength is 4 cm)

<i>Main Technical Specifications</i>	<i>Values</i>
Swath Width, m	6; 12; 16
Distance Between Aircraft Axis and Swath Beginning, m	0.6; 2.6 4
Spatial Resolution, m	7680 (wavelength=3.9 m)
Nominal Frequency, MHz	pulse
Type of Signal Radiated	VV – vertical-vertical
Polarization	8
Digitizer Resolution, bits	

SAR-23 (radiation wavelength is 23cm)

Main Technical Specifications

	Values
Swath Width, □m	16
Spatial Resolution, m	8
Nominal Frequency, MHz	1300 (wavelength=23 □□)
Type of Signal Radiated	pulse
Polarization	VV; HH – horizontal-horizontal; VH – vertical-horizontal;
Digital Resolution, bits	HV – horizontal-vertical 8

MICROWAVE RADIOMETER (MWR). It uses for detection edge between difference water mass types along flight track under research aircraft. It is all-weather system.

Main Technical Specifications

	Values
Frequency Range, GHz	5.150-5.900
Measured Temperature Range, °□	0...400
Sensitivity, °□	no more 0.1
Accumulation Time, s	1.4
Antenna	mouthpiece
Nominal Power, W	no more 10

Besides, above remote sensing equipments use digital photo- and video cameras. Digital photo camera is “NIKON D1X”, digital video camera is “PANASONIC NV-MX7D”. All data put on aircraft PC in real time and position simultaneously and automatically on base GPS using.

For connection with vessels and other ground center uses standard radio equipment - VHF (“Sailor) and aircraft short-wave equipment, also onboard aircraft has “Inmarsat-C”.

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